

European
Commission

The Birth Day Prize is brought to you in collaboration with:

BILL & MELINDA
GATES foundation

MSD
MSD for mothers
Committed to Saving Lives

© European Union, 2015. Image: © pim #68635620, 2015. Source: Fotolia.com.

Part B

« QUARITE »

QUALITY of care, Risk management and obstetric TEchnology: a multifaceted intervention to reduce hospital-based maternal and neonatal mortality in poor resource setting

Dr. Alexandre DUMONT
Institut de Recherche pour le Développement

List of contestant(s)

Contestant No *	Contestant organization name	Country
1 (Coordinator): Alexandre Dumont	Institute Research for Development	France
2 Pierre Fournier	University of Montreal	Canada

* Please use the same contestant numbering as that used in the administrative application forms.

Table of Contents

1. ABSTRACT.....3

2. INTRODUCTION.....5

 Where did the idea come from? 5

 How did the solution emerge? 5

 How was the solution implemented? 7

 How to measure the impact of this solution? 10

3. DETAILED DESCRIPTION OF THE PROPOSED SOLUTION..... 14

 A. Is the solution effective to reduce hospital-based maternal and newborn mortality? 14

 B. Is the solution safe? 37

 C. Has the solution the potential for rapid scalability? 41

 Is the solution replicable in settings of intended use? 47

 Is the application acceptable to health care providers? 50

 Is the application economically viable for the settings in which it is intended? 56

 Is the solution usable by facility-based health workers? 59

GENERAL CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS 64

REFERENCES..... 67

1. ABSTRACT

In the early 2000s, progress in reducing global maternal mortality in sub-Saharan Africa was insufficient. Most of these deaths occurred in referral hospitals and were preventable. Effective and cheap interventions exist to prevent death from major causes, including haemorrhage, hypertensive disorders and sepsis. What was lacking was evidence on implementation with regards to local contexts, resource constraints and cultural norms. Together with colleagues, I developed a managerial solution based on education, audits and outreach to improve quality of care and prevent maternal and perinatal deaths in health facilities providing emergency obstetric care in low-income countries.

After a pilot study in Senegal to test this solution, I did a pragmatic cluster-randomised controlled trial in 46 referral hospitals in Senegal and Mali, referred to as the *QUARITE Trial*. Data for more than 190,000 women was collected over 4 years, giving the study the power to detect a change in mortality. The intervention was based on the Society of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists of Canada ALARM (Advances in Labour And Risk Management) International Program and combined maternal death reviews (or audits), leadership development, training in emergency obstetric care, and outreach health practitioner education. Hospitals allocated to the control group did not partake in the intervention and continued their usual care. The results showed a **15% greater reduction in maternal deaths** in the intervention compared to the control hospitals over 4 years (odds ratio [OR] 0.85, 95% CI 0.73–0.98, $p=0.0299$). The most impressive difference in maternal death occurred **in district hospitals, where a 35% greater reduction in death was seen** (adjusted OR 0.65; 95% CI 0.55–0.77, $p<0.0001$). The intervention also resulted in a **decrease of neonatal mortality within 24 h** (adjusted OR 0.74; 95% CI 0.61–0.90, $p<0.0023$). This reduction could be explained by the overall quality improvement in intrapartum care. There was other evidence that the intervention changed practice. Positive changes were shown in the management of three major conditions leading to maternal death including pre-eclampsia, post-partum haemorrhage, and sepsis.

As part of the pilot study in Senegal and the QUARITE trial, I and colleagues from the **social sciences** conducted three consecutive surveys in participating hospitals regarding safety concerns and implementation outcome variables. The intervention ensured to cover all safety concerns and to avoid any ethical and safety restraint for patients or healthcare professionals. We did not observe any unintended effects of the audits, such as litigation or staff resignation. There were no particular health risks for the patients because we did not introduce new drugs or new

Directorate-General for Research and Innovation

Horizon Birth Day Prize

diagnostic tests. **The solution is replicable in various contexts**, over a large scale, as demonstrated in the QUARITE trial. **Health professionals and service administrators were receptive and adhered relatively well to the process and the results** of the audits, as evidenced by the number of maternal death cases audited, and the relevance of the recommendations drawn by the local audit committees. Education and outreach facilitated maternal death reviews by providing healthcare professionals with the accurate knowledge and confidence to make quality improvement suggestions during the audit sessions. Concerning the costs associated with the intervention building at a national level and the implementation costs at a hospital level, **the application is economically viable for the settings in which it is intended**. The total amount of resources required for four years represents less than 1% of the resources allocated for referral hospitals in the countries where the trial was carried out. The audit approach is easy to use when the information collected for the audit is appropriate and local leadership is strong enough to promote non-threatening and multidisciplinary audit meetings.

These findings confirm the evidence from observational studies in sub-Saharan Africa that **maternal audits** are **effective, replicable, well accepted**, easy to use and affordable. When supported with education, audit can prevent some maternal and neonatal deaths, yet wider societal changes are still needed. These results are important for policy makers and could contribute to the success of the new approach introduced by the World Health Organization in 2012 called “Maternal Death Surveillance and Response (MDSR)”.

2. INTRODUCTION

Where did the idea come from?

I am a senior scientist at the Institute of Research for Development (IRD) and Obstetrician-Gynaecologist-. After training as a doctor in the 1990s, I worked for several years in referral hospitals in Senegal (Africa) as an obstetrician-gynaecologist. I rapidly felt that the organisation of care could play a very important role in maternal and child survival in this country where mortality was very high at this time [Hogan 2010]. My research activity was then consistently focused on **Emergency Obstetric and Neonatal Care (EmONC)** services, subsequently exploring all the determinants related to the quality of care. Through this field research, I became interested in quality-insurance programs, which had been developed in my home country several years earlier (France).

How did the solution emerge?

With colleagues from the Roi Baudouin district hospital of Dakar in Senegal, I first experienced the audit approach in 2000-2003. I understood that reviewing maternal deaths and complications was a promising method that may make pregnancy safer in this setting [Dumont 2006]. I therefore reviewed the different strategies for implementing best practices in obstetric environment [Chaillet 2006]. The results of this systematic review have shown that educational strategies with medical providers were generally ineffective; educational strategies with paramedical providers, opinion leaders, quality improvement and educational outreach visits had mixed effects; clinical audit and feedback, reminders, and multifaceted strategies were generally effective. Moreover, the proportion of effective strategies was significantly higher among the interventions including a prospective identification of barriers to change compared to standardised interventions.

Several barriers to improving quality of care were present in my work environment in Senegal. I was confronted with structural problems affecting the healthcare system and the recurring problem of the lack of qualified human resources. This deficit translated into both an insufficient health workforce and difficulty in maintaining a high-quality performance in healthcare professionals in a low-resource setting. Moreover, the lack of motivation and incentives led to a significant drain of the most qualified personnel and to a delegation of tasks to less qualified staff. For all these reasons, I chose to develop a multifaceted intervention to address the different barriers to overcome, combining continuing education, audits and feedback, quality

Directorate-General for Research and Innovation

Horizon Birth Day Prize

improvement, opinion leader and educational outreach visits. The definition, theory and assumptions of each active ingredient of the “**multifaceted intervention**” are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Active ingredients of the solution

Active ingredient	Definition	Theory	Assumption
Continuing education	Any educative strategy, as workshop or conference, intended to persuade providers to change their performance and maintain their competences.	Cognitive and learning theories	Undesirable behaviour is caused by a lack of information and skills.
Audit and feedback	An external or internal systematic and critical analysis of the quality of the medical care with feedback to local providers	Behavioural and learning theories	Behaviour is a result of external stimuli, and change occurs through the participation of professionals in analysing their practices
Opinion leader	Clinicians identified by their colleagues in the community as being respected clinicians and effective communicators	Social learning and innovation theories, social influence and power theories	Change occurs through the interaction and influence of important people
Quality improvement	Quality improvement is a modification of existing systems, structures, and tasks to improve quality of care	Management theories, system theories	Errors can be prevented by improving the design of health systems and processes
Educational outreach visit	A knowledgeable person visits each target clinician to explore a problem and possible local solutions, discuss their concerns, and provide attractive documents summarising key facts	Health promotion, innovation, and social marketing theories	Behaviour can be changed with clear and attractive products and messages that meet a target audience need

How was the solution implemented?

The implementation of this multifaceted intervention needed the collaboration of different partners. The first one was the *World Health Organization (WHO)* with which I contributed to developing a guide called “**Maternal Death Review**” (**MDR**). The MDR was directed at health professionals, healthcare planners and hospital managers to audit maternal deaths in healthcare facilities. **The approaches described go beyond just counting deaths and develop an understanding of why they happened and how they can be averted** [Beyond the numbers 2004]. The second main partner was the *Society of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists of Canada (SOGC)*. Together with colleagues, in 2007 I helped to develop the 4th edition of the Advances in Labour and Risk Management International Program, or AIP [ALARM 2007]. This continuous education program was designed to train health professionals providing obstetrical care in developing countries. The five-day program reviewed the top maternal killers and suggested essential tools and problem management with the goal of improving care for mothers and newborns. Other partners were the *Ministries of Health of Senegal and Mali, Ob-Gyn and midwife associations, and professors of gynaecology and obstetrics in both countries.*

This collaborative work with national partners helped me to identify opinion leaders and knowledgeable people in each country to facilitate the implementation of the multifaceted intervention.

The sequence of activities was meant to fit into a two-year program **directed towards developing local leadership and empowering obstetric teams in referral hospitals in developing countries** [Dumont 2014]. To meet this objective, the intervention was carried out over several steps (Figure 1). The intervention began with the recruitment of “opinion leaders” in each participating hospital, trained in best practices and in maternal death audits (training the trainers). Each opinion leader was then in charge of creating obstetric teams in their own centres that were in charge of implementing the maternal death audits and organising best practices staff training with the support of external facilitators (educational outreach visits).

Figure 1: Key steps in the implementation of the intervention

Step 1 - Training of opinion leaders: The local opinion leaders are responsible for maternity services in the participating hospitals (one doctor and one midwife per centre). The opinion leaders took part in the five-day training session of the AIP [ALARM 2007]. The program was updated biannually. The session included three days of training in EmOC best practices, one day of training in maternal death audit techniques and one day of awareness training related to economic, sociocultural and ethical barriers (including sexual and reproductive rights). At the end of the session, a normative evaluation was carried out by certified instructors from SOGC. No financial incentive was given to the health workers involved in the program.

Step 2 - Creating and training a multidisciplinary audit committee (doctors, midwives, nurses, and administrators), according to the following schedule: 1) identification and training of data collectors on maternal deaths; 2) training of the committee members in the process of carrying out audits; and 3) annual summary of audit results.

Step 3 - Launching the audit cycle: with the support of external facilitators, the audit process was set in motion by the audit committee in each hospital in accordance with the approach proposed by WHO [Beyond the numbers 2007] (see Figure 2). Monthly audit meetings were recommended to analyse cases of maternal deaths in each facility.

Figure 2: Maternal death audit cycle in hospitals. Source Dumont 2006

Step 4 - Training qualified staff in best practices: The local opinion leaders, supported by the external facilitators, trained the professionals in each health facility according to the following schedule: 1) evaluation of needs for best practices training; and 2) organisation of four to eight training sessions annually. The topics were selected by local opinion leaders according to the principal causes of maternal mortality identified during maternal death reviews. If needed, a local opinion leader who had taken part in the initial training workshop could develop new clinical guidelines or update existing guidelines according to EmOC best practices.

Educational outreach visits by external facilitators: A knowledgeable person, chosen for his or her expertise and leadership visited participating hospitals every three months. The purpose of these visits was to support the local opinion leaders in their role of providing AIP training to all the health professionals in the maternity unit and to ensure that audits were being carried out, particularly by overseeing an audit meeting. To promote evidence-based practice, meetings with the hospital's professionals and administrators were encouraged, as well as clinical observation periods related to the topics that were taught.

Recertification of the opinion leaders: Trainees in the participating hospitals attended two recertification sessions (once a year for two years). They underwent an accelerated training session (three days), led by certified instructors from SOGC. The purpose of this recertification

session was to verify the opinion leaders' knowledge, update them on the clinical content and process of maternal death audits, discuss their roles, share their experiences and confirm their capacity to provide leadership in their clinical settings.

How to measure the impact of this solution?

My primary assumption was that the solution **reduced** the overall rate of **maternal mortality** in participating hospitals, measured as the vital status of the mother (dead or alive) at hospital discharge.

My secondary assumption was that the program reduced the number of **stillbirths** and early **neonatal death**.

Measuring these maternal and child outcomes was a major issue in African healthcare facilities because the data quality of medical records was poor. I used the Performance of Routine Information System Management (PRISM) framework to design, strengthen and evaluate the existing health information system in the different hospitals participating to the research [Aqil 2009]. My objective was to ascertain all maternal and newborn deaths occurring in these healthcare facilities.

This approach targeted three categories of determinants of the performance of Routine Health Information System (RHIS): technical, behavioural and environmental/organisational (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Performance of routine information system management (PRISM) framework. Source Aqil 2009

In each participating hospital, I identified one or two local collaborators to collect the clinical data: a nurse or a midwife. These collaborators received financial incentives for this specific task. We asked them to complete a standard form for each patient giving birth in the participating centre. This form included information on maternal characteristics, prenatal care, labour and delivery, diagnosed complications, and the vital status of both mother and child upon discharge from hospital (see patient registration form, appendix 1). The number of variables to be collected was limited to 30 (38 in the case of a triple birth) and constituted a core set of outcome measures to evaluate maternity care [Devanne 2007]. The data were collected on an ongoing basis. This information was extracted from the hospital registers and from available medical records. If medical records were lacking, we introduced them, using the model of the WHO partogram, with the support of the head of the maternity unit. The medical records were stored in a secure location.

Data quality and medical record archiving were regularly monitored by a research assistant. Variables from the standard form were registered using epi-info software. The electronic record was periodically verified by a data manager. All information collected on patients was confidential.

Access to the clinical database was restricted to the data manager and the head of the maternity unit.

The quality control of clinical data was carried out in three stages:

- First, the research assistant verified that the data collection was exhaustive by comparing the number of patients on the hospital's birth register with the number of patient forms collected. A further procedure was carried out to monitor the thoroughness of data on maternal deaths, which were generally under-registered on the maternity ward. The procedure had identified the eligible maternal deaths among all the female deaths that occurred in the facility using the various registries available: admissions, hospitalisations (maternity and other departments), operating rooms, and morgue. On a random sample of patient forms, the research assistant checked the quality of data collected. The completion rate was estimated according to the proportion of patient forms containing 100% of the following information: date of entry, patient identification, date of discharge, and vital status of the mother and newborn at the date of discharge. The concordance rate was estimated as the proportion of patient forms with information corresponding to the hospital registers and medical records. Both completion rate and concordance rate were expected to be above 75%. If the completion or concordance rate was between 50% and 75%, the research assistant checked the data quality on a new random sample of patient forms. A completion or concordance rate of less than 50% triggered the verification of all patient forms.
- A second check for missing or abnormal data was carried out before data entry. If necessary, the missing information was obtained from the local data collectors of each facility.
- The third step was carried out by the data manager after the data had been entered. An audit report of the database, including lists of duplications and missing or abnormal data, was shared with the local data collector and the head of the maternity unit responsible for correcting any errors.

Figure 4: Overview of the process & quality management

3. DETAILED DESCRIPTION OF THE PROPOSED SOLUTION

A. Is the solution effective in reducing hospital-based maternal and newborn mortality?

With a consortium of international researchers, in 2007-2011 we conducted a cluster randomised controlled trial referred as the *QUARITE Trial* to evaluate the effect of the multi-faceted intervention in referral hospitals with high maternal mortality rates [Dumont 2013]. The trial was funded by the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR). The CIHR had no further role in the conduct of this research project or the interpretation of its results.

Setting and participants

We chose to carry out the study in Mali and Senegal where maternal mortality rates were very high at this period: 970 and 980 maternal deaths per 100,000 live births, respectively [Hogan 2010]. Emergency obstetric care coverage was poor (around 15%). On the other hand, according to United Nations indicators, enough referral hospitals were equipped with functional operating rooms. However, the quality of care in these referral centres was inadequate, as evidenced by high case fatality rates (above 1%) [Otchere 2007].

The public health system, which was practically the only provider of modern healthcare services in both countries, was based on primary healthcare facilities or community health centres, district hospitals, regional hospitals and national or teaching hospitals. Whereas the latter offer comprehensive emergency obstetric care, community health centres provide only basic obstetric services, including assisted deliveries. When an emergency complication arises in the community health centre, the patient is referred to a district or regional hospital. Mild complications were managed at the first level of care - the district hospital. Patients requiring more specialised healthcare services were referred to second level care - regional or national hospitals. In the capital cities of both countries (Dakar in Senegal and Bamako in Mali), both first- and second-referral hospitals were available. Disparities were apparent in the resource allocation and geographical accessibility between hospitals in Dakar and Bamako and hospitals outside the capitals.

The trial consisted of a one-year pre-intervention or baseline period (year 1), a two-year intervention period (years 2 and 3), and a one-year post-intervention period (year 4), when the

primary outcome was assessed. First- and second-level public referral hospitals with more than 800 deliveries per year that had a functional operating room and had not previously carried out maternal death review were eligible to participate (Figure 5). Centres were included on the basis of formal, informed consent from the hospital director and the person in charge of maternity services. Women giving birth in each of the participating facilities during the study period were included. Women who delivered at home or in another centre but were transferred postnatally were excluded.

Figure 5: Eligible referral hospitals in the QUARITE Trial (identified in blue)

Study design

We used a stratified cluster randomised parallel-groups trial design. The hospital was the unit of randomisation, in order to avoid contamination between practitioners in the same service, as the intervention directly targeted teams of professionals. Hospitals were stratified by country and into three hospital types (hospitals in the capital, regional hospitals, and district hospitals outside the capital). To ensure a balance in the number of deliveries per year between hospitals assigned to the two groups, stratum blocked randomisation was used. Each block included two hospitals

of similar size. Investigators were informed of the allocation status of the individual hospitals only after the completion of collection of baseline data and, shortly before the first five-day training session of the AIP.

The formula for calculating the required number of patients is the one used for a cluster-randomised controlled trial design. The calculation was based on an overall maternal mortality rate of 1.5% in the pre-intervention phase and an expected reduction of 30% of maternal mortality in the hospitals of the intervention group, in comparison with the control group. In order to account the clustering of the outcomes within hospitals, we used the Intra-class Correlation Coefficient (ICC) estimated in the pilot study in Senegal [Dumont 2009]. The calculation showed that a total of 38,205 patients and 46 hospitals (38,205/830) allowing us to achieve a power of 82% to detect a 30% reduction in hospital-based maternal mortality between groups (OR = 0.70) with 2-sided significance test at $\alpha = 0.05$ and with ICC = 0.001 (ACluster-design®2005, version 2.0, World Health Organization).

Intervention

The multifaceted intervention in the experimental group was implemented over a two-year period at the hospital level and following the sequence of activities presented above (Figure 1). The hospitals randomised to the control arm did not receive any intervention from the research team. Administrators of these hospitals were informed that a six-day training workshop would be provided at the end of the trial. The objective of this workshop was to train “opinion leaders” in each control hospital as we did in the intervention hospitals.

Outcomes and blinding

Primary outcome

The primary outcome was hospital-based maternal death, measured as the vital status of the mother (dead or alive), at hospital discharge. A system of data collection, independent from the intervention process, was set up in all participating hospitals. This system was based on the WHO global survey on maternal and perinatal health in Africa [Shah 2008].

All deliveries carried out in participating centres were registered by local data collectors (appropriately trained nurses or midwives). They completed a standard form for each eligible

patient that included information on maternal characteristics, prenatal care, labour and delivery, diagnosed complications, and the vital status of both mother and child at hospital discharge. This information was extracted from the hospital registers and from available medical records whose quality and archiving procedures were regularly monitored by the country-level study coordinators. Special attention was paid to ascertain all maternal deaths as described previously using the PRISM framework.

All data was collected on an ongoing basis throughout the study and transferred to the national coordinating centre for double data entry using Epi-Info 2000 software. The electronic records containing the clinical data were cleaned on a quarterly basis, then transferred to the trial's main coordinating centre in Montreal for quality control, and stored in a secure location. An independent Data Security and Monitoring Board (DSMB) performed two blinded interim analyses at the end of the first and second year of intervention and, based on their results, recommended continuation of the trial.

The data collection and the implementation of the intervention were carried out by different and independent organisations in each country. The organisations were not blinded with respect to randomisation but they were not involved in the assessment of the outcome. Until the end of the study, access to the clinical database was restricted to the data manager in Montreal, Canada.

Secondary outcomes

We also assessed the effects of the intervention on three types of secondary outcomes: perinatal mortality, medical practice for emergency obstetric care and resource availability in each hospital.

- Perinatal deaths were assessed for all singleton pregnancies and were defined as either **stillbirth**, early **neonatal deaths** that occurred within the first 24 hours after birth and those that occurred later but before hospital discharge and within 28 days.
- Medical care was evaluated through the following essential obstetric interventions, considered **effective in reducing maternal and perinatal mortality**: **assisted delivery** (forceps and vacuum extraction), **caesarean section**, **transfusion** and **hysterectomy**, or **transfer to another more specialised health facility**.

- Availability of resources required to provide high-quality emergency obstetric care in the African context, as proposed by the World Health Organization, was quantified by the ‘hospital complexity index’ [Shah 2008]. We assessed the separate effects of the intervention on the total complexity index score and on each of its eight sub-scores, corresponding to the availability of specific resources (listed in the lower part of Table 6). For each hospital, the index was calculated separately for the baseline and year 4, based on a systematic, standardised inventory of available resources.

Analysis

The intervention effect on the *primary outcome* was estimated as the difference between the allocation groups in the change of individual mothers’ risk of hospital-based mortality from the baseline (year 1) to the post-intervention (year 4) period.

Primary Intention-To-Treat (ITT) analyses used hospital-based death of individual mothers as the binary individual-level outcome and relied on the generalised estimating equations (GEE) extension of the logistic regression model, with exchangeable covariance structure, to account for the clustering of women within hospitals. Using the difference-in-differences approach, additional reduction of the risk that a mother would die before being discharged from hospital in the intervention group, relative to the reduction in the control group, was estimated by the odds ratio with 95% Confidence Intervals (CI) for the interaction between indicators of the trial arm (intervention vs. control) and time (year 4 vs. 1) from the GEE model. The GEE model-based two-sided Wald test of this interaction, at $\alpha = 0.05$, was used to test the significance of the intervention effect.

The GEE model was adjusted according to two stratification variables: hospital type and country. It was also adjusted according to variables selected “a priori” as potential risk factors for hospital-based mortality, including both (a) baseline (year 1) characteristics of hospitals (availability of adult intensive care unit, blood bank, anaesthetist, and obstetrician-gynaecologist) and (b) characteristics of individual women (residence, age, parity, previous caesarean delivery, any pathology during pregnancy, prenatal visit attendance, multiple pregnancy, referral from another health facility, ante- or postpartum haemorrhage, pre-eclampsia/eclampsia, prolonged/obstructed labour, uterine rupture, puerperal infection/sepsis).

Because of the small number of hospitals in each of the six strata, as well as major differences in both the resources available in particular hospitals and the characteristics of women who delivered in the different hospitals, **such adjustments were important to minimise potential confounding bias**. Interactions with each of the two stratification variables were tested at two-tailed $\alpha = 0.05$ to assess whether the intervention effect varied by hospital type or country. If the interaction was significant, the intervention effects were reported separately for each stratum of the respective variable.

All individual-level *secondary binary outcomes*, related to either medical practice or perinatal deaths, were analysed using the same methods as described above for the primary outcome. The only difference was that, for some outcomes, the multivariable GEE logistic models, accounted for clustering of outcomes within the hospitals, did not converge. This occurred whenever a given outcome was not observed at all in any of the mothers or infants, in some hospitals among the 46 participating hospitals. For those outcomes, we reported the results of a corresponding conventional multivariable logistic regression, fitted at the preliminary stage of GEE analyses. The Odds Ratio (OR) estimated through the conventional logistic regression models is known to be quite similar to the corresponding GEE-based ORs, but the standard errors are systematically under-estimated when the logistic model, ignoring clustering, is fitted to clustered data. Therefore, for all outcomes analysed with logistic regression, we used a conservative cut-off of $p < 0.001$ as a criterion for 'statistical significance' to account for the spuriously low p-values.

To assess the effect of the intervention on the resource availability, quantified by the hospital complexity index score, we adapted the difference-in-differences approach (DID) of the primary outcome to the analyses of a quantitative hospital-level outcome. Specifically, for the total complexity score and for each of its eight sub-scores, we estimated the multivariable mixed linear model, with 46 hospitals as the unit of the analysis. Exchangeable covariance structure was assumed to account for the correlation of the two complexity scores, for year 1 (baseline) and year 4 (post-intervention), within the same hospital. The multivariable mixed linear model adjusted the effects of the year, the randomisation group and their interaction for the two stratification variables (country and hospital type). The statistical significance of the intervention effect was assessed by testing the year-by-group interaction, which indicated whether the mean change in the complexity scores (year 4 – year 1) over time differed between the two trial arms.

To include all eligible women in the ITT analyses, missing data on individual characteristics were imputed based on their distributions in the study population. In sensitivity analysis, women who died before labour were excluded because these women usually sought care only after developing severe complications at home. It was often too late to prevent death by the time these women were admitted into the referral hospital, and we hypothesised that the multifaceted intervention could not have changed the outcomes for these very high-risk women. All analyses were performed with SAS version 9.2 statistical software.

Results

The trial flow chart is presented in Figure 4. Of the 49 eligible hospitals, 46 accepted to participate and were included in the trial. No hospital was lost to follow-up.

Figure 6- Study flow diagram. MDR = Maternal Death Review; SD = Standard Deviation

We identified 1,067 qualified healthcare professionals (doctors, midwives, and nurses) in the maternity units at trial entry (536 in Senegal and 531 in Mali). Staff turnover was low in participating hospitals (overall 3% per year). In both countries, obstetric care was provided by doctors, midwives, and registered nurses with midwifery training. Staff specialised in anaesthesia (nurse or doctor) participated in the management of complicated cases. During the baseline period, the mean number of qualified personnel per hospital was 22.5 (SD = 22.9) within the intervention hospitals and 26.7 (SD = 27.7) within control hospitals. These figures did not markedly change during the post-intervention period (Table 2).

The mean annual number of deliveries was 1,843 (SD = 1472) and 1,936 (SD = 1218) respectively for the intervention and control hospitals. Overall, 197,336 patients were enrolled during the baseline and post-intervention periods (97,982 in intervention and 99,354 in control arms). Clinical records were not retrieved for 6,169 (3%) patients, and no information except the date of delivery was available for these women: 2,051/97,982 (2.1%) and 4,118/99,354 (4.1%) respectively in the intervention and control arms. These women were excluded from the analyses. Since we identified all the female deaths that occurred in the participating hospitals using the various registries available (admissions, hospitalisations, operating rooms, and morgue), we assumed that none of these patients with no data available died during their hospital stay.

In total, 191,167 patients who delivered in the participating hospitals were analysed (95,931 and 95,236 in the intervention and the control arms, respectively).

Table 2. Characteristics of hospitals by group allocation during the baseline period (year 1) and the post-intervention period (year 4), data presented as mean (standard deviation) or number of hospitals (%)

	Year 1		Year 4	
	Intervention (n=23)	Control (n=23)	Intervention (n=23)	Control (n=23)
Mean number of qualified personnel per hospital (standard deviation)	22.5 (22.9)	26.7 (27.7)	20.9 (12.9)	21.6 (12.7)
Doctors	3.0 (1.7)	3.2 (1.7)	3.3 (2.1)	4.3 (3.1)
Midwives	9.7 (8.9)	9.4 (9.4)	6.1 (6.3)	6.4 (5.7)
Nurses with midwifery training	7.2 (14.7)	10.8 (18.1)	7.9 (6.4)	8.3 (5.3)
Nurses with anaesthesiology training	2.7 (1.6)	3.3 (3.6)	2.7 (2.3)	2.6 (2.4)
Country: n (%)				
Hospitals in Mali	11 (47.8)	11 (47.8)	11 (47.8)	11 (47.8)
Hospitals in Senegal	12 (52.2)	12 (52.2)	12 (52.2)	12 (52.2)
Type of hospital: n (%)				
Hospital in the capital	6 (26.1)	6 (26.1)	6 (26.1)	6 (26.1)
Regional hospital outside the capital	7 (30.4)	7 (30.4)	7 (30.4)	7 (30.4)
District hospital outside the capital	10 (43.5)	10 (43.5)	10 (43.5)	10 (43.5)
Level of care*: n (%)				
First-level referral hospital	15 (65.2)	16 (69.6)	15 (65.2)	16 (69.6)
Second-level referral hospital	8 (34.8)	9 (39.1)	8 (34.8)	9 (39.1)
Resource availability per hospital: n (%)				
Obstetrician- gynecologist on staff	17 (73.9)	15 (65.2)	17 (73.9)	18 (78.3)
Physician specialised in anaesthesia on staff	12 (52.2)	10 (43.5)	11 (47.8)	10 (43.5)
Staff member specialized in anaesthesia (nurse or physician) available 24/24	7 (30.4)	11 (47.8)	10 (43.5)	8 (34.8)
Blood bank	14 (60.9)	13 (56.5)	17 (73.9)	16 (69.6)
Adult intensive care unit	8 (34.8)	9 (39.1)	9 (39.1)	8 (34.8)

* Mild complications were managed in the district hospital, which constituted the first level of care. Patients needing more specialised healthcare services were referred to the regional or national hospital, i.e. to the second level of care.

Hospital and patient characteristics

The infrastructural capabilities of the participating hospitals were associated with the level of care. The personnel were more qualified (i.e., specialist obstetrician-gynaecologists, doctors specialised in anaesthesia) and the health services were more specialised (i.e., intensive care unit, blood bank, microbiology laboratories) in second-level than in first-level referral hospitals.

Among the 12 hospitals in the capital cities (Bamako and Dakar), three were second-level referral teaching hospitals and nine were first-level referral hospitals. The 14 regional hospitals outside the two capital cities were all second-level referral hospitals, and the 20 district hospitals were all first-level referral hospitals.

The characteristics of the participating hospitals and patients in the two trial-arm comparisons are shown in Tables 2 and 3. Essential resources for EmOC did not markedly change during the study period, except for the number of blood banks, which increased in both allocation groups but remained somewhat more frequent in the intervention hospitals (Table 2). The availability of staff specialised in anaesthesia differed between the two groups.

The two groups also differed in some patient characteristics in the baseline year: the proportion of women who lived outside the area of the hospital, had an obstetric complication or had an emergency caesarean delivery (ante- or intrapartum) was higher in intervention hospitals than in control hospitals (Table 3). These differences could partly explain why women in the intervention arm had a higher pre-intervention crude hospital-based mortality rate (Table 4). There was no missing data on hospital characteristics, while for patient characteristics the proportion of missing data varied from 0% for parity to a maximum of 1% for age.

Table 3. Characteristics of patients by group allocation during the baseline period (year 1) and the post-intervention period (year 4), data presented as number of patients (%)

	Year 1		Year 4	
	Intervention (n=43,269)	Control (n=41,655)	Intervention (n=52,662)	Control (n=53,581)
Residence:				
In the city of the hospital	36974 (85.4)	35782 (85.9)	45560 (86.5)	47272 (88.2)
Outside the city but in the same region	4008 (9.3)	5125 (12.3)	5957 (11.3)	5386 (10.1)
Outside the region	2242 (5.2)	509 (1.2)	1115 (2.1)	854 (1.6)
Age ≥ 35 years	4356 (10.1)	4195 (10.1)	5325 (10.1)	5210 (9.7)
Nulliparous	28435 (65.7)	26939 (64.7)	35908 (68.2)	36397 (67.9)
Previous caesarean delivery	3112 (7.2)	2782 (6.7)	5196 (9.9)	4920 (9.2)
Any pathology before pregnancy*	406 (0.9)	324 (0.8)	516 (1.0)	648 (1.2)
No prenatal visit	4221 (9.8)	4535 (10.9)	4780 (9.1)	5250 (9.8)
Any pathology during current pregnancy**	3976 (9.2)	3401 (8.2)	3897 (7.4)	4834 (9.0)
Multiple pregnancy	1768 (4.1)	1555 (3.7)	2139 (4.1)	2135 (4.0)
Referred from another health facility	11644 (26.9)	9384 (22.5)	15382 (29.2)	13097 (24.4)
Forceps/vacuum extraction	921 (2.1)	854 (2.1)	1019 (1.9)	1068 (2.0)
Elective caesarean delivery (CD)	920 (2.1)	954 (2.3)	1711 (3.2)	1786 (3.3)
Emergency ante-partum CD	1627 (3.8)	966 (2.3)	2256 (4.3)	1110 (2.1)
Emergency intra-partum CD	6483 (15.0)	5268 (12.6)	8963 (17.0)	8931 (16.7)
Any obstetric complication	10585 (24.5)	9533 (22.9)	13599 (25.9)	14136 (26.4)
Ante- or postpartum haemorrhage	2743 (6.3)	2477 (6.0)	3165 (6.0)	2869 (5.4)
Pre-eclampsia/eclampsia	1758 (4.1)	1233 (3.0)	2385 (4.5)	2172 (4.0)
Prolonged/obstructed labour	7173 (16.6)	6649 (16.0)	9725 (18.5)	10937 (20.4)
Uterine rupture	321 (0.7)	248 (0.6)	348 (0.7)	267 (0.5)
Puerperal infection/sepsis	242 (0.6)	428 (1.0)	354 (0.7)	216 (1.4)
Blood transfusion	1220 (2.8)	1074 (2.6)	1644 (3.1)	1310 (2.4)
Hysterectomy	127 (0.3)	114 (0.3)	152 (0.3)	115 (0.2)
Transportation to another hospital	72 (0.2)	83 (0.2)	53 (0.1)	35 (0.1)

* HIV, chronic respiratory conditions, cardiac or renal diseases, sickle-cell trait, chronic hypertension; ** pyelonephritis or urinary infection, malaria, severe maternal anaemia (<7 g/dl), gestational diabetes, pregnancy-induced hypertension, vaginal bleeding near full term, chorioamnionitis.

Primary outcome

Crude hospital-based maternal mortality in the baseline period was higher in regional hospitals than in capital and district hospitals in both allocation groups (Table 4). During the study period, the secular trends of crude maternal mortality rates in regional hospitals were similar in the intervention and

Directorate-General for Research and Innovation

Horizon Birth Day Prize

control groups. In contrast, in both capital and district hospitals, crude mortality decreased markedly in the intervention group while it increased slightly in the control group (Figure 7a). There was a steady decline in the intervention hospitals in the capital cities. For the district hospitals outside the capital cities, the benefit was demonstrated later (year 4) following the education program.

Figure 7a. Hospitals in capital city

Figure 7b. District hospitals outside the capital

Figure 7c. Regional hospitals outside the capital

Figure 7. Trends in crude hospital-based maternal mortality

In multivariable GEE analyses that accounted for clustering and were adjusted for hospital and patients' characteristics, the post-pre-intervention reduction of hospital-based maternal mortality in intervention hospitals was significantly greater than the reduction in control hospitals (adjusted OR = 0.85; 95% CI: 0.73–0.98, $p = 0.0299$), Table 4. However, there was a statistically significant interaction with hospital type ($p < 0.05$). Analyses that accounted for this interaction indicated that the benefits of the intervention were limited to capital city hospitals (adjusted OR = 0.86; 95% CI: 0.74–0.99, $p = 0.0374$) and district hospitals (adjusted OR = 0.65; 95% CI: 0.55–0.77, $p < 0.0001$), with no significant effect for regional hospitals (adjusted OR = 1.02; 95% CI: 0.79–1.31, $p = 0.89$).

The exclusion of maternal deaths before labour from the analyses did not substantially change the results (e.g. adjusted OR = 0.84; 95% CI: 0.73–0.97, $p = 0.0229$ for the effect pooled across hospital types). The intervention effects did not vary significantly across the two countries (OR = 1.11 for the interaction with the country; 95% CI: 0.83–1.48, $p = 0.47$).

Ante- or postpartum haemorrhage, pre-eclampsia/eclampsia and indirect causes (anaemia, malaria, HIV/AIDS, and cardiovascular disease) were the leading causes of hospital-based maternal deaths in both groups (Table 5). In the post-intervention period, we observed a marked decrease in the number of deaths related to haemorrhage, pre-eclampsia/eclampsia and puerperal infection in the intervention group.

Table 4. Primary outcome. Data is presented as number of maternal deaths per 1000 patients (crude hospital-based maternal mortality rates) by group allocation and period.

	Intervention group			Control group			Effect of the intervention		
	Baseline rate (number of patients)	Rate in Year 4 (number of patients)	Rate change*	Baseline rate (number of patients)	Rate in Year 4 (number of patients)	Rate change*	Difference in rate change (95% CI)	Adjusted OR ** (95% CI)	<i>P</i> value
Hospitals in the capital	2.5 (52/20543)	1.4 (39/27615)	- 1.1	2.8 (46/16704)	3.2 (73/23032)	0.4	-1.4 (-2.9 – -0.2)	0.86 (0.74-0.99)	0.0374
Regional hospitals	18.1 (241/13305)	15.5 (204/13135)	- 2.6	13.3 (211/15906)	10.2 (189/18499)	- 3.0	0.4 (-3.4 – 4.3)	1.02 (0.79-1.31)	0.8911
District hospitals	16.1 (152/9421)	9.5 (113/11912)	- 6.6	8.8 (80/9045)	9.9 (119/12050)	1.0	-7.6 (-11.7 – -3.6)	0.65 (0.55-0.77)	<0.0001
Total	10.3 (445/43269)	6.8 (356/52662)	- 3.5	8.1 (337/41655)	7.1 (381/53581)	- 1.0	- 2.5 (-4.2 – -0.9)	0.85 (0.73-0.98)	0.0299

* Rate change, post-intervention period – pre-intervention rate

** Additional reduction of the risk that a mother in the intervention group would die before being discharged from hospital, relative to the reduction in the control group, adjusted for country, hospital characteristics (availability of adult intensive care unit, blood bank, anaesthetist, and obstetrician-gynaecologist) and patient characteristics (age, parity, previous caesarean delivery, any pathology during pregnancy, prenatal visit attendance, multiple pregnancy, referral from another health facility, ante- or postpartum haemorrhage, pre-eclampsia/eclampsia, prolonged/obstructed labour, uterine rupture, puerperal infection/sepsis). Clustering was taken into account using generalised estimating equations (GEE) models and interchangeable structure of the residual

Table 5. Causes of hospital-based maternal mortality by group allocation during the baseline (year 1) and post-intervention period (year 4), data presented as number of maternal deaths (%)

Cause of death	Intervention group		Control group	
	Year 1	Year 4	Year 1	Year 4
Uterine rupture	32 (7.2)	24 (6.7)	25 (7.4)	24 (6.3)
Haemorrhage	144 (32.4)	122 (34.3)	111 (32.9)	128 (33.5)
Pre-eclampsia/eclampsia	101 (22.7)	63 (17.7)	78 (23.1)	85 (22.3)
Obstructed labour	5 (1.1)	2 (0.6)	4 (1.2)	3 (0.8)
Puerperal infection/sepsis	41 (9.2)	21 (5.9)	15 (4.5)	26 (6.8)
Other direct causes*	25 (5.6)	29 (8.1)	34 (10.1)	19 (5.0)
Other indirect causes**	95 (21.3)	95 (26.7)	68 (20.2)	94 (24.6)
Unclassified	2 (0.4)	0 -	2 (0.6)	1 (0.3)
Total	445 (100)	356 (100)	337 (100)	381 (100)

* Excluding uterine rupture, most common direct causes of maternal death were: ante- or postpartum haemorrhage, pre-eclampsia, obstructed labour and puerperal infection, the complications during surgery or anaesthesia, suspected amniotic fluid embolism and thrombo-embolism (not confirmed by autopsy).

** Anaemia, malaria, HIV/AIDS and cardio-vascular disease were the most common indirect causes of maternal death.

Secondary outcomes

Table 6 summarises the results for secondary outcomes related to perinatal mortality, medical practice and resource availability. In the case of a statistically significant interaction with the country or the hospital type, separate intervention effects are reported, respectively, for Mali and Senegal or for capital, regional and district hospitals.

The study intervention resulted in a **marginally significant decrease in neonatal mortality before 24h** (adjusted OR = 0.74, 95% CI: 0.61 – 0.90, p=0.0023 in logistic model) and no significant effects on stillbirths (adjusted OR = 1.05, 95% CI: 0.91 – 1.22, p=0.48). Finally, the effects on **neonatal mortality after the first day of life varied considerably depending on hospital type**, with a **significant decrease in capital hospitals** (adjusted OR = 0.24, 95% CI : 0.13 – 0.45, p<0.0001), **no effect in district hospitals** (adjusted OR = 0.81 95% CI : 0.41 – 1.62, p=0.56) and **marginally significant increase in regional hospitals** (adjusted OR = 2.36, 95% CI : 1.36 - 4.09, p=0.0022 in logistic model).

Secondly, the intervention resulted in **significant increase in the probability of transfusions** (overall effect was marginally significant, adjusted OR = 1.44, 95% CI: 0.99 - 2.11, $p=0.06$), especially in regional hospitals (adjusted OR = 2.32, 95% CI: 1.52 - 3.55, $p<0.0001$). Furthermore, the probability of emergency **ante-partum caesarean deliveries increased significantly** (adjusted OR = 1.33, 95% CI: 1.19 - 1.50, $p<0.0001$). The main indications for ante-partum caesarean delivery were pre-eclampsia and eclampsia (27% of all ante-partum caesareans). In contrast, the **overall frequency of intra-partum caesarean deliveries decreased significantly** (adjusted OR = 0.87, 95% CI: 0.82 - 0.92, $p<0.0001$), but the effects **varied significantly by country and hospital type**. Specifically, the study intervention had no effect on the probability of intra-partum caesarean deliveries in the capital hospitals, whereas for regional and district hospitals it decreased in probability in Senegal but increased in Mali. The main indications for intra-partum caesarean deliveries were prolonged/obstructed labour or suspected cephalopelvic disproportion (37%) and foetal distress (16%). The overall frequency of assisted deliveries (forceps or vacuum) increased in Senegal (adjusted OR = 3.10, 95% CI: 1.85 - 5.20, $p<0.0001$), with no effect in Mali (adjusted OR = 0.51, 95% CI: 0.16 – 1.59, $p=0.25$).

Finally, the **intervention had no effect** on the overall **resource availability**, as the increases over time in the total score for the hospital complexity index were similar for the two trial arms. However, the improvements over time in the mean scores reflecting the provision of clinical protocols and training were significantly greater in the intervention than in the control group.

Table 6: Secondary outcomes: perinatal mortality.

Data is presented as a percentage (crude hospital-based rates) by group allocation and period.

Perinatal outcomes ^a : % (n)	Intervention group			Control group			Effect of the intervention	
	Baseline	Year 4	Change	Baseline	Year 4	Change	Adjusted OR (95% CI)*	P value
Stillbirth (G)	9.39% (3883/41368)	8.40% (4238/50426)	-0.99%	8.60% (3441/39992)	8.32% (4270/51324)	-0.28%	1.05 (0.91 - 1.22)	0.4828
Neonatal mortality before 24h (L)	1.16% (434/37485)	0.97% (446/46188)	-0.19%	0.90% (332/36551)	1.07% (505/47054)	0.17%	0.74 (0.61 - 0.90)	0.0023 *
Neonatal mortality after 24h and before hospital discharge (L)	0.62% (232/37485)	0.40% (185/46188)	-0.22 %	0.27% (99/36551)	0.21% (99/47054)	-0.06%	0.88 (0.63 - 1.25)	0.4826
Hospitals in Capital	0.44% (83/18894)	0.13% (33/25576)	-0.31%	0.20% (31/15499)	0.18% (38/21140)	-0.02%	0.24 (0.13 - 0.45)	<.0001 **
Regional hospitals	1.00% (108/10757)	1.00% (107/10737)	0%	0.34% (45/13229)	0.18% (28/15600)	-0.16%	2.36 (1.36 - 4.09)	0.0022 *
District hospitals	0.52% (41/7834)	0.46% (45/9875)	-0.06%	0.29% (23/7823)	0.32% (33/10314)	0.03%	0.81 (0.41 - 1.62)	0.5564

(G) or (L) indicates which of the 2 alternative types of multivariable models were used to estimate the adjusted effect of the intervention on the specific outcome:

(G): The results of the generalised estimating equation (GEE) model, with exchangeable structure of the residual covariance matrix to take into account the clustering, are presented whenever the GEE model converged;

(L) alternatively, the logistic model was fitted when the GEE model did not converge.

For both types of model, the intervention effect is shown as the adjusted OR (95% CI). Adjusted OR presents the additional change in the odds for the risk of perinatal death, relative to the concurrent change (from year 1 to year 4) in the control group, adjusted for country, hospital type and hospital, characteristics, patient characteristics and birth weight (for perinatal outcomes). Overall effect is always reported; the Subgroup-specific effects are reported only if there is significant interaction with the corresponding stratification variable (i.e. Country and/or Hospital type).

In GEE models $p < 0.05$ is considered significant and indicated by **, while * indicates $0.05 < p < 0.06$, i.e. a 'marginally significant' effect; in logistic models, because of under-estimated variance, only $p < 0.001$ is considered "significant" (see Methods) and indicated by **, while * indicates $0.001 < p < 0.003$, i.e. a 'marginally significant' effect.

^a Perinatal outcomes were assessed for singleton births only, excluding multiple pregnancies from the analysis.

Table 6: Secondary outcomes (continue) – medical practice

Data is presented as a percentage (crude hospital-based rates) by group allocation and period

Medical practice: % (n)	Intervention group			Control group			Effect of the intervention	
	Baseline	Year 4	Change	Baseline	Year 4	Change	Adjusted OR (95% CI)*	P value
Elective caesarean delivery (G)	2.13% (920/43269)	3.25% (1711/52662)	1.12%	2.29% (954/41655)	3.33% (1786/53581)	1.04%	0.92 (0.68 - 1.26)	0.6261
Emergency ante-partum caesarean delivery (L)	3.76% (1627/43269)	4.28% (2256/52662)	0.52%	2.32% (966/41655)	2.07% (1110/53581)	-0.25%	1.33 (1.19 - 1.50)	<.0001 **
Emergency intra-partum caesarean delivery (L)	15.92% (6483/40722)	18.41% (8963/48695)	2.49%	13.26% (5268/39735)	17.62% (8931/50685)	4.36%	0.87 (0.82 - 0.92)	<.0001**
<hr/>								
Hospitals in Capital	10.78% (745/6914)	17.60% (1280/7273)	6.82%	9.72% (649/6677)	13.21% (884/6690)	3.49%	0.87 (0.75 - 1.02)	0.0936
Senegal Regional hospitals	21.02% (2072/9855)	19.15% (1818/9493)	-1.87%	15.04% (1600/10635)	25.03% (2670/10667)	9.99%	0.45 (0.40 - 0.50)	<.0001 **
District hospitals	6.65% (306/4599)	9.40% (506/5385)	2.75%	2.17% (75/3456)	4.50% (195/4332)	2.33%	0.59 (0.43 - 0.81)	0.0011 *
<hr/>								
Hospitals in Capital	14.40% (1778/12350)	14.80% (2718/18365)	0.40%	14.06% (1278/9087)	16.87% (2535/15029)	2.81%	0.93 (0.84 - 1.04)	0.2125
Mali Regional hospitals	23.58% (586/2485)	41.77% (1013/2425)	18.19%	13.96% (610/4370)	16.75% (1090/6507)	2.79%	2.23 (1.87 - 2.67)	<.0001 **
District hospitals	22.04% (996/4519)	28.24% (1628/5764)	6.20%	19.17% (1056/5510)	20.87% (1557/7460)	1.70%	1.25 (1.08 - 1.44)	0.0021 *
<hr/>								
Forceps/vacuum extraction (G)								
Senegal	1.25% (279/22368)	2.24% (496/22151)	0.99%	1.76% (366/20768)	0.65% (142/21689)	-1.11%	3.10 (1.85 - 5.20)	<.0001**
Mali	3.32% (642/19354)	1.97% (523/26544)	-0.35%	2.57% (488/18967)	3.19% (926/28996)	0.62%	0.51 (0.16 - 1.59)	0.2460

Table 6: Secondary outcomes (continue) – resource availability

Data is presented as the mean (complexity index) by group allocation and period

Hospital Complexity Index ^b : mean (SD)	Intervention group			Control group			Adjusted effect of the intervention	
	Baseline	Year 4	Mean Change	Baseline	Year 4	Mean Change	Difference between Mean Changes (95% CI)	P value
Basic services	6.78 (0.52)	6.87 (0.34)	0.09	6.74 (0.62)	6.74 (0.92)	0	0.09 (-0.29 - 0.47)	0.6454
General medical services	13.87 (3.51)	15.09 (4.75)	1.22	13.52 (4.79)	15.35 (4.17)	1.83	-0.61 (-2.49 - 1.27)	0.5179
Laboratory tests	8.96 (1.62)	8.74 (1.32)	-0.22	8.78 (1.35)	9.22 (1.35)	0.44	-0.65 (-1.54 - 0.23)	0.1446
Anaesthesia resources	4.43 (0.73)	4.61 (1.75)	0.18	4.22 (1.57)	4.39 (1.59)	0.17	4.12E-15 (-0.98 - 0.98)	1
Emergency obstetric care	10.26 (1.84)	10.96 (1.66)	0.70	9.30 (2.30)	10.04 (2.23)	0.74	-0.04 (-0.79 - 0.70)	0.907
Intrapartum care	8.22 (1.44)	9.30 (1.61)	1.08	8.70 (1.87)	8.91 (1.50)	0.21	0.87 (-0.26 - 1.99)	0.1265
Human resources	8.43 (3.41)	9.57 (3.40)	1.14	8.48 (3.64)	9.35 (3.69)	0.87	0.26 (-1.30 - 1.83)	0.7386
Protocol and training	5.48 (1.90)	7.30 (1.15)	1.82	7.04 (0.98)	7.00(2.37)	-0.04	1.87 (0.70 - 3.03)	0.0023
Total (all of the 8 categories)	66.43 (8.25)	72.43 (10.52)	6.00	66.78 (12.50)	71.00 (10.51)	4.22	1.78 (-1.95 - 5.51)	0.3539

^b The range of service available in each of the facilities was assessed using an adapted version of the complexity index developed for the WHO Global Survey project in African countries (Shah 2008) This index comprised eight categories reflecting the: standard of building/basic services, maternal intrapartum care and human resources; availability of general medical care, anaesthesiology, emergency obstetric services and provision of screening tests and academic resources and clinical protocols. The original hospital complexity index was used by WHO in Latin America and Asia and adapted for use in Africa. We implemented minor adaptations to reflect the context of Mali and Senegal. The maximum total score (all of the 8 categories) in one hospital is 100.

Interpretation of the results

Hospital-based **maternal mortality was reduced by 15% in Mali and Senegal** in the year following the 2-year intervention to promote MDR and on-site training in emergency obstetric care. The intervention was particularly **effective in reducing maternal deaths from haemorrhage and pre-eclampsia/eclampsia**. The intervention resulted in **medical practice changes** (increase in the probability of transfusions and ante-partum caesareans for hypertensive complications), considered to be effective in reducing maternal mortality. The decrease in intra-partum caesarean deliveries could also have contributed to the improvement of maternal outcomes, as this mode of delivery is associated with increased risks among mothers in Mali and Senegal [Briand 2012]. The effect of the multifaceted intervention was limited to capital and district hospitals, which mainly acted as first-level referral hospitals in this trial. The lack of effect in second-level referral (regional) hospitals outside the capitals may be due to potential contamination bias. Indeed, during the period of this trial, international (bilateral cooperation) and governmental organisations implemented MDR and on-site training in four out of the seven regional hospitals in the control group.

The **lack of effect on stillbirth** is not surprising as the intervention did not specifically target prenatal care, which is considered effective in reducing foetal intra-uterine deaths. In contrast, the **decrease in neonatal mortality within 24 h** could be explained by the overall quality improvement in intra-partum care and changes in the mode of delivery. On the other hand, the effect of the intervention on **neonatal mortality after 24 h varied considerably depending on the type of hospital**. The likely reason is that other possibly unmeasured neonatal and institutional variables might have influenced neonatal outcomes after the first day of life.

These findings confirm the evidence from observational studies in sub-Saharan Africa that maternal audits are effective. It is difficult to compare the effect of this intervention with other controlled studies in similar contexts. We searched PubMed for cluster randomised controlled trials, before-and-after studies and studies that used interrupted time series analyses carried out in low- or middle-income countries and published in English between January 1, 1970, and December 31, 2016, with the following search string: (“maternal mortality” [MeSH] AND “maternal death review” [MeSH]) OR (“maternal mortality” [MeSH] AND “in-facility death audits” [Text Word]) OR (“maternal mortality”[MeSH] AND “confidential enquiries” [Text Word]) OR (“maternal mortality”[MeSH] AND “audit and feedback” [Text Word]) OR (“maternal mortality”[MeSH] AND “Educational outreach visits ” [Text Word]) OR (“emergency obstetric care training”[Text Word]) OR (“obstetric audit”[Text Word]). We found no randomised trials and five before-

and-after and interrupted time series studies [Martey 1993, Mburaku 1995, Dumont 2006, Kongnyuy 2008, and van den Akker 2011] that assessed the effects of the implementation of the audit approach on maternal and/or neonatal mortality. Most papers on the effectiveness of training in EmOC describe positive reactions, increased knowledge and skills, and improved behaviour after training, but **fail to show improved maternal outcomes** [Jamtvedt 2006]. Observational or quasi-experimental studies in sub-Saharan countries on the effect of critical incident audits and feedback (including maternal death) suggested a decrease in hospital-based maternal mortality ranging from 27% to 80%, but failed to control for concurrent reduction in mortality, reflecting secular trends.

The innovative aspect and ambition of the QUARITE trial is that it was one of the largest trials on hospital-based maternal mortality in sub-Saharan Africa. The participant hospitals were representative of the existing health system in both countries, taking into account the full variety of contexts and levels of care. The large database (approximately 100,000 patients per year) and the system of data control we implemented in all participating hospitals allowed us to obtain reliable information on maternal outcomes [Dumont 2009]. Thus, this trial provides strong evidence to promote MDR and on-site training in referral hospitals in low-resource settings.

Potential limitations of this trial should be taken into account in interpreting our results. First, data is restricted to hospital-based maternal deaths; therefore, maternal mortality in the population cannot be inferred. We have no data on trends of deaths outside of the hospital environment, however it is unlikely that the reduction in hospital-based deaths, and especially the incremental reduction observed in the first-level hospitals in the intervention groups, could be explained by an increase in out-of-hospital deaths.

Despite our efforts to ascertain all maternal deaths, it is possible that some eligible women with no data available died before discharge. As the frequency of these women with no data was very low and twice as high in the control group (4.1% vs 2.1%), the assumption that none of these women died before discharge could not explain a significant reduction of mortality in the intervention hospitals. Moreover, the QUARITE trial was a pragmatic cluster randomised controlled trial carried out in two countries with ongoing national programs designed to reduce maternal mortality. The most relevant programs that could potentially have had an impact on hospital-based maternal mortality implemented during this research were: (i) the free caesarean section programs launched in 2005 in Mali and Senegal to reduce the financial barrier for caesarean deliveries (patients did not pay for surgery, supplies or drugs); and (ii) the national maternity

referral system launched in 2002 in Mali to improve access to EmOC services. The free caesarean section program was implemented in all referral hospitals in Mali and Senegal, except in the capital, Dakar [Witter 2010]. Strengthening the referral system involved all referral hospitals in Mali [Fournier 2009]. For these reasons, these co-interventions were balanced between the hospitals in the two allocation groups. This 'balance' ensured that the incremental reduction of maternal mortality observed in the intervention group, relative to simultaneous changes in mortality in the control group, could not be attributed to concurrent implementation of the aforementioned programs. Accordingly, such co-interventions should not affect the results regarding the effectiveness of our multifaceted intervention. Finally, activity related to data collection may also have had an impact on quality improvement and maternal outcomes in participating hospitals. However, this 'data collection' effect was, a priori, similar in the two groups (intervention versus control).

Conclusion

Facility-based maternal death reviews combined with educational outreach visits by a trained external facilitator are effective in reducing hospital-based maternal and immediate neonatal mortality in first-level referral hospitals with high mortality rates. This multifaceted intervention was particularly effective in reducing maternal death from direct obstetric causes (ante- or postpartum haemorrhage, pre-eclampsia/eclampsia and puerperal infection). The preventive strategies and treatments for these complications are well known. Our educational program facilitated the implementation of these best practices. Further studies are needed to determine whether the benefits of this intervention are generalisable to second-level referral hospitals.

B. Is the solution safe?

I conducted a survey in participating hospitals regarding safety concerns. I assumed that on-site training activities and maternal death reviews could monopolise healthcare providers and divert them from clinical tasks. Moreover, during the audit meetings I verified whether the findings of MDR were used to blame healthcare providers.

Method

I undertook a survey in participating hospitals in both control and intervention groups during the post-intervention period of the QUARITE trial regarding maternal death reviews and continuous education practices. I collected detailed information on specific activities implemented during the intervention period in each participating hospital using in-depth interviews with health services managers and healthcare providers.

Results

Regular educational outreach visits by a certified instructor to promote MDR and continuous medical education occurred in all intervention hospitals. National support from opinion leaders varied somewhat between Senegal and Mali. A professor from the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology of the University of Bamako took part in all visits in Mali. In Senegal, an obstetrician-gynaecologist from the National Reproductive Health Office visited only half of the intervention hospitals during the first supervision and did not take part in the other visits.

Most intervention hospitals collected information on maternal mortality, planned regular meetings for MDR and trained staff personnel in emergency obstetric and neonatal care (EmONC). But these activities are time-consuming for healthcare providers. Table 7 shows the mean duration for key activities in each hospital in Senegal and Mali. Some of the managers interviewed said that the time spent to fully implement the intervention was binding and could interact with clinical tasks, but was compatible with the standard activity of a referral hospital in Mali or Senegal.

Table 7: Mean time to implement key activities of the multifaceted intervention

	Senegal (N=12 hospitals)	Mali (N=11 hospitals)
Set up the process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · One meeting · 2 h 40 min. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Two meetings · 1 h 30 min. and 2h 20 min.
Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 13 professionals in District hospitals, 11 in Regional Hospitals, et 22 in capital hospitals. · 5 sessions / year · Mean duration = 3h. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 11 professionals in District hospitals, 10 in regional hospitals, 20 in capital hospitals. · 7 sessions / year · Mean duration = 1h 45 min.
Collect in the hospital	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · By doctor or midwife. · Mean duration / case = 1h 45 min. · Mean Nb of cases by year = 15 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · By doctor or midwife (sometimes resident or nurse) · Mean duration / case = 2 h 15. · Mean Nb of cases / year = 15
Verabl autopsy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · By midwife · Mean duration / case = 3 h. · 3 hospitals conducted verbal autopsy · Mean Nb of cases / year= 1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · By Nurse or doctor · Mean duration / case = 4 h 30 min. NB: for one hospital = 3 days · 5 hospitals conducted verbal autopsy · Mean Nb of cases / year = 3
Audit session	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 6 sessions / year · 15 professionals in District hospitals, 12 in Regional hospitals, et 9 in capital hospitals · Mean duration by case = 30 min. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 7 sessions / year · 13 professionals in District hospitals, 14 in Regional hospitals, et 12 in capital hospitals · Mean duration by case = 45 min.
Feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Prepare the annual meeting = 9 h. · by Ob-Gyn 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Prepare the annual meeting = 13 h. · by Ob-Gyn

In the hospitals of the intervention arm, the audit meetings were held every two or three months depending on the number of cases to be audited. Between six and 23 people per hospital (median = 13) attended these meetings. Additionally, the local trainers on each site organised between four and eight training sessions in best practices during the intervention period in their own hospitals, with the support of external facilitators. Between eight and 38 people per hospital (median = 15) attended these sessions. The most recurrent training topics were pre-eclampsia and post-partum haemorrhage management. **These training activities were highly valued in each hospital.**

There are certain essential prerequisites to limit the time-consuming effects of MDR and on-site training for healthcare professionals. During the preliminary phases of implementation, we ensured that someone with experience and authority accepted overall responsibility for the coordination and that a reasonable part of the work in the hospital was dedicated to educational activities. We enhanced existing health information systems in each participating hospital (see the PRISM framework in Figure 3) and ensured that each centre had a reasonable level of record-keeping in terms of registering deaths, retrieving case notes and the quality of recording the notes. This point was essential to avoid wasting time when collecting the information. We agreed with local authorities that health professionals initiating and/or conducting MDR needed the required authority and support. A protocol of what was intended was supplied in each hospital

Directorate-General for Research and Innovation

Horizon Birth Day Prize

to help healthcare professionals to conduct the reviews. A MDR team was created and trained. This team had the main responsibility for conducting the review, although the collaboration with a number of other people was essential. The team consisted of two to four individuals, with a balanced mix of professions and skills. The team could, for example, consist of a nurse-midwife, an obstetrician, a public health doctor and someone with community experience such as a community health worker or a traditional birth attendant. Each of the team members had different responsibilities for gathering data, depending on their skills. To select these collaborators, the most important criteria were that the members should have an interest in, and commitment to, investigating maternal deaths, and be able to devote sufficient time to the work to be done. In some of the participating hospitals, **a community element was part of the review**. In these cases, we recommended that the data collector have knowledge of the local language and the ability to develop relationships with community members. The inclusion of at least one senior person was important (opinion leader), to give the team some authority and facilitate relationships with local authorities and other agencies.

I observed **no unintended effect of MDR, such as litigation or staff resignation**, in any of the hospitals.

There are a **number of legal and ethical issues** that need to be considered when investigating maternal deaths in referral hospitals. I took into account the laws, customs and culture of Mali and Senegal to access medical information, involve families and healthcare professionals in the data collection process, conduct the audit sessions and use the findings. The supportive health policy framework in each country, which encourages the ongoing investigation on maternal deaths, facilitated the process. Families and healthcare professionals participated well in the reviews or provided information to local data collectors. In order to keep the study completely **anonymous** (local data collector could know the names of the women and the healthcare workers), no identifying information was reported on the forms, and each data collector or supervisor was responsible for anonymity before sending any report form to the assessors for completion. They had to maintain confidentiality and ensure that the record was securely kept when not in use. Privacy was an ethical consideration that was important for both families and healthcare workers. On the one hand, the deceased and her family had the right to privacy, but on the other hand it was almost impossible to investigate a maternal death and maintain complete privacy. Relatives and healthcare workers were assured that, as far as possible, privacy was maintained, and confidentiality was kept concerning the identities of the deceased women investigated, their families and healthcare professionals involved in their care. Only investigators could have access to such data. Data collection forms, case summaries,

Directorate-General for Research and Innovation

Horizon Birth Day Prize

review meetings and any reports or dissemination of results did not contain personal identification. This was particularly necessary when the death occurred as a result of an illegal abortion. The research team recommended to health services managers that information not be used to blame individuals or institutions, nor to punish persons or groups. In some rare cases, investigations that were carried out in a manner seeking to attribute blame for an adverse event inhibited the willingness of people to cooperate with the process. This key principle, named “no name, no blame” was reiterated at each audit session. On the other hand, health workers needed to be accountable for their actions. Accountability was encouraged by carrying out on-site training in a way that sought to improve quality of care.

Conclusion

The QUARITE trial made sure to cover all safety concerns, so that there was not ethical and safety issue from the point of view of patients or healthcare professionals. There were no particular health risks because we did not introduce new drugs or diagnostic tests. Easy access to information, qualified data collectors and leadership of services managers are key principles to limiting the effects of audits and training activities on healthcare professionals’ time.

C. Does the solution have the potential for rapid scalability?

As part of a pilot study in Senegal and the QUARITE Trial in Senegal and Mali, I carried out, together with colleagues from the social sciences, three consecutive surveys regarding implementation outcomes variables: **adoption** of the audit approach, **acceptance** by healthcare providers and health service managers, **feasibility** in different types of referral hospitals, **fidelity** of the key components of the multi-faceted intervention and **implementation cost**. These variables can all serve as indicators of the success of implementation and could inform policy makers on the potential for rapid scalability. This complementary research aimed to assess how well implementation has occurred and to provide insights about how this contributes to the reduction of hospital-based maternal or neonatal mortality.

The first survey started in May 2004, at the beginning of the preparatory phase for the audits, and finished in July 2005, at the end of the six-month MDR pilot-testing period in five referral hospitals in Senegal. The second survey started in September 2008, at the beginning of the scaling up of the intervention in 23 participating hospitals in Mali and Senegal (QUARITE trial), and finished in September 2010. The last survey started in March 2011, during the post-intervention period of the QUARITE trial, and finished in July 2011. Figure 8 presents the timeline of the different implementation research activities.

	Pilot study (2004-2005)	QUARITE Trial (2007-2011)			
		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Interviews and observations (survey 1)					
Baseline clinical data collection					
Implementation of the solution					
Interviews and observations (survey 2)					
Post-intervention clinic. data collection					
Interviews and observations (survey 3)					
Costs assessment					

Figure 8: Timeline of implementation research activities before and during QUARITE trial

Methods

We carried out focus-group discussions, participant observations of audit meetings, analysis of audit documents (data collection forms, audit report forms, minutes and lists of attendance at meetings) and interviews with staff in the participating hospitals, according to the different surveys.

Survey 1

MDRs were implemented in five pilot reference hospitals from May 2004 to June 2005, with external support from the *National Department of Reproductive Health (NDRH) of the Ministry of Health in Senegal* and a *non-governmental organisation (CEFOREP)*.

The MDR method was introduced in three stages:

- First, a national workshop was held in May 2004 with the heads of the maternity units to present the methodology of MDR and the related research activities. A standardised data collection form to collect information about maternal mortality cases and a framework of case management analysis was developed with auditing tools from previous studies carried out in Senegal.
- Secondly, audit meeting guidelines were prepared and audit committee members from each hospital, including managers, were trained on-site to identify and analyse maternal mortality cases from September-December 2004.
- This preparatory phase was followed by a six-month pilot-testing period of the audit approach in each hospital (from January to June 2005). One member of the NDRH and one member of the CEFORP visited the maternity units to supervise the audit activities. The findings, audits process and objectives were reviewed during these visits, with periodic adjustments in methods to better implement the MDR in the various settings.

Three focus groups were conducted by the research team in three hospitals at the beginning of the preparatory phase (May 2004), with four to six participants (doctors and midwives), according to the hospital. Focus groups were separated across hospitals and mixed across professional groups; the discussion lasted approximately two hours and focused on three main themes: determinants of maternal mortality and advantages and disadvantages of maternal deaths reviews.

Eight participant observation sessions were conducted by the research team in five hospitals in Senegal during the audit's six-month pilot-testing period (from January to June 2005). Prior to the visit of the research team, the heads of the maternity units were asked to prepare an audit meeting that would take place on the same day as the visit. Observers were focused on taking notes, including on non-verbal observations and recording and observing the audit meeting. Audit documents (data collection forms and audit session reports) of previous meetings were collected by the observers for quantitative analysis.

At the end of the six-month pilot-testing period of the audits in Senegal, interviews with staff were conducted in July 2005 by a qualified professional (midwife) trained in using the questionnaire. Health authorities provided the research team with lists of health professionals in each facility. The areas of focus defined for interviews were: sociodemographic characteristics of the health worker; professional qualifications; length of service in the hospital; perception of maternal mortality in the country and in the hospital specifically; participation in training sessions, in the data collection for maternal deaths and in audit sessions; existence of feedback; perception of barriers to and facilitators of MDRs implementation. Among the 121 listed professionals of the pilot maternity units, we interviewed the personnel currently on staff at the time of the researchers' visits in the health facility (between two and four days in each centre). Sixty-six (54%) individuals were interviewed: 15 obstetrician-gynaecologists, six other medical practitioners (paediatricians, anaesthesiologists, and biologists), 31 midwives, 11 paramedics, three other hospital staff members. Once the information sheet had been explained, each participant provided written consent. Since the majority of the personnel we interviewed had not yet participated in the audit meetings (it was the initiating phase of the audit process), interviews were conducted accordingly: respondents were asked to describe their perceptions of maternal mortality in their country and in their hospital specifically, barriers and challenges encountered when implementing MDRs and factors and interventions they believed important to facilitating and supporting the audit approach in their hospital. Data collectors (5/5) and heads of the maternity units (4/5) took part in in-depth interviews that further defined their own specific tasks in implementing MDRs.

Focus group discussions, participant observations, semi-structured questionnaires and in-depth interviews were conducted in French or in Wolof. At the participants' request and to ensure confidentiality, sessions were not audiotaped. Researchers reconstructed detailed notes immediately after each survey and translated them into French if appropriate. Together with field-notes, they entered data into a computer by means of Microsoft Office Word software.

Survey 2

This survey took place during the intervention period phase of the QUARITE trial. Twenty-one participant observation sessions were conducted during audit meetings by the research team in participating hospitals of the intervention group. The trial coordinator also collected detailed information on specific activities

implemented during the intervention period in each participating hospital using in-depth interviews with health services managers and analysis of audit documents.

To assess whether the MDR activities were implemented with high consistency by comparison to what was intended, we defined ten follow-up indicators (Table 8). The selection of these indicators was based on the recommendations of the World Health Organization [Beyond the numbers 2004]. The indicators were compared against data extracted from the program documents (data collection forms, meeting and supervision minutes and logbook) to evaluate whether a minimal standard of the MDR implementation has been met. A checklist of 10 questions related to each expected standard of MDR implementation was completed by the study coordinator at each visit in the 23 intervention hospitals during the two-year intervention period. For each affirmative response, a point was given. An implementation score (on a scale from 1 to 10) was calculated for each centre during each visit (a total of 8 visits).

Table 8: Follow-up indicators for MDR implementation

	Point
1. A local committee for MDR has been created	1
2. Data collector on maternal deaths has been trained	1
3. Guidelines for MDR implementation are available	1
4. Data collection forms are used appropriately	1
5. Data collection forms, case summaries, meeting reviews and reports are securely kept	1
6. Most maternal death cases are reviewed (> 80%)	1
7. Recommendations are clear and realistic	1
8. Avoidable factors are identified	1
9. Confidentiality is assured (no name, no blame)	1
10. The grid analysis for maternal death cases review is used appropriately	1

MDR: maternal death reviews

Survey 3

This survey took place during the post-intervention period of the QUARITE trial. We conducted in-depth interviews with health authorities, policy makers and health services managers of the intervention hospitals in the post-intervention period (from March to July 2011) to assess the recommendations of the local audit committees and incremental implementation costs.

Implementation costs were assessed at two levels. The first level was national and represented the resources that the government used to carry out activities outside hospitals (e.g. initial training and recertification, supervision and coordination). The second level was in hospital: hospitals had to bear a financial and non-financial burden through their participation in the program. As mentioned previously, activities related to in-service training and MDR needed time and involvement of staff and health service managers. The information used for the calculation of personal costs comes from the audit documents and interviews, except for salaries, per diems and transportation costs that were obtained from official sources in Senegal and Mali. Costs incurred during the preparatory phase of the intervention have been taken into account.

The costs at a national level are related to the following activities: (1) development of teaching materials (2) initial training and recertification meetings, (3) quarterly visits (supervision), and (4) national coordination costs. Table 9 shows the cost items for each of these activities and the sources of information mobilised.

Table 9: Implementation costs at the national level

ACTIVITY	METHOD OF COSTS ESTIMATION	SOURCE OF INFORMATION
1. Development of teaching materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Costs related to updating clinical guidelines - Costs related to the dissemination of teaching materials in participating hospitals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Interviews with coordinators – Interviews with health service managers
2. Training opinion leaders and recertification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Personal cost — Instructors (2 in Senegal and 3 in Mali) - Personal cost — opinion leaders (participants in Senegal and Mali) - Costs related to the organisation, transport, accommodation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – List of participants – Interview with instructors – Salaries (Ministry of health)
3. Supervision visits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Per diem for the supervisor (76 days per year) - Costs related to transport, accommodation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Per diem rates (Ministry of health)
4. National coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial incentives for the national coordinator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Interview with the national coordinator

The personal costs at a hospital level referred to the time spent by healthcare professionals on MDR implementation. We identified six types of processes in which staff were involved in the audit cycle (Table 10): (1) time spent setting up the audit Committee (number of meetings, participants and duration of meetings) (2) time spent by participating staff on in-service training, (3) time spent by the collector completing the data collection forms, (4) time spent on investigation in the community (verbal autopsy), (5) time spent attending the audit sessions and the time required to complete the report, and (6) time spent by the person responsible for the drafting of the annual report of the findings for feedback.

Several data sources were used to measure the level and costs of activities in hospitals (the audit cycle) and program costs at the national-level:

- Project documents: the budget of the Society of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists of Canada provided information on the costs of teaching material and training. The QUARITE trial documents were collected to know the frequency and the attendance of each audit and learning sessions held each year.
- Interviews were conducted between January and May 2010 in both countries to investigate the time spent by each hospital on audit cycle activities. N=23 chief doctors (in some cases chief-midwives) had to identify the person in charge of the audit cycle activities and the estimated time needed to: 1) collect and fill the audit file per case, 2) hold the audit session and complete the report, 3) collect information for verbal autopsy and 4) prepare the annual report. Additional information on the time spent in learning sessions was asked as well.
- The Ministries of Health in both countries provided information on per diem rates and salaries for health professionals. We assumed that the time allocated for each of these activities in hospitals was similar for the two first years of the intervention with supervision, and for the last year of the trial without supervision.

Table 10: Implementation cost at the hospital level

ACTIVITY	METHOD OF COSTS ESTIMATION	SOURCE OF INFORMATION
1. Setting up the process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Personal costs – member – Number of staff involved 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Interviews with key stakeholders – List of the committee members – Salary rates (Ministry of health)
2. On-site training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Personal costs - participant – Number of participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Interviews with key stakeholders – List of the committee members – Salary rates (Ministry of health)
3. Collect in the hospital	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Personal costs - data collector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Interviews with data collectors – Salary rates (Ministry of health)
4. Verbal autopsy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Personal costs - data collector – Transportation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Interviews with data collectors – Salary rates (Ministry of health)
5. Audit sessions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Personal costs - participant – Number of participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Interviews with key stakeholders – List of the committee members – Salary rates (Ministry of health)
6. Feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Personal costs - opinion leader 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Interviews with opinion leaders – Salary rates (Ministry of health)

Is the solution replicable in settings of intended use?

Results

After my first experience of MDR in Roi Baudouin district hospital, I coordinated a feasibility study in five pilot hospitals in Senegal before scaling up the multi-faceted intervention in 23 hospitals in Senegal and Mali. I report here the extent to which MDR was carried out in different countries and settings (**feasibility**) and the actions of health stakeholders to try to employ this new intervention (**adoption**) at different time of the research program.

First observation in Roi Baudouin district hospital

As described above, my first experience of MDR implementation took place in one referral healthcare centre in the Dakar area of Senegal between 2000 and 2003 [Dumont 2006]. My observations suggested that MDR was **feasible in resource-poor settings** and could be effective in reducing maternal mortality in health facilities. Several factors contributed to the successful implementation of MDR in this hospital. The most important factors were: quality-controlled data collection and computerised patient records, a strong **commitment** to the project from the head of the maternity unit, a strong executive-coordination

team and provision of annual written feedback to staff, support from health authorities and community representatives, and an equitable and successful cost-recovery system.

The pilot study in five referral hospitals in Senegal (survey 1)

The Ministry of Health in Senegal initiated maternal deaths reviews in five pilot hospitals in 2004 [Dumont 2009]. This initiative was the initial step of a national program that aimed to scale up MDR in all referral health facilities that offer emergency obstetric care in Senegal. The five hospitals were purposely selected to include facilities in Dakar, the capital, as well as other areas with various characteristics. They were also selected to include primary-level referral hospitals (district) and more specialised (regional and/or teaching) hospitals with various characteristics (Table 11).

Table 11: Characteristics of participating hospitals in the pilot study in Senegal (2004-2005)

Characteristic	Hospital A Teaching/ tertiary level	Hospital B District	Hospital C Regional	Hospital D Regional	Hospital E Regional
Localisation in Dakar (capital city)	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
No. of maternity beds	120	66	54	86	33
No. of doctors covering maternity	7	2	1	3	1
No of midwives	41	21	9	9	5
No of deliveries (2004)	6345	7426	2959	4378	648
Availability of basic services ^a	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Availability of obstetric services ^b	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Availability of caesarean sections ^c	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Availability of safe blood ^c	No	No	No	No	No
Availability of adult intensive care unit	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Number of maternal deaths (2004) ^d	53	44	31	60	37
Overall rate of maternal lethality/1000 ^e	8.3	5.9	10.5	13.7	57.1

^a Reliable water supply, sanitation facilities, electricity, generator, refrigerator, telephone

^b Parenteral antibiotics, Parenteral oxytocic drugs, parenteral anticonvulsants for preeclampsia and eclampsia, manual removal of placenta, removal of retained products (e.g., vacuum aspiration), assisted vaginal delivery (e.g., vacuum extraction, forceps)

^c caesarean section and transfusion can be done in the service 364 days a year, 24 ha day

^d Source of information: registers of deliveries in the maternity units for year 2004

^e Number of maternal deaths among women giving birth in the facility during the same period

According to the results of survey 1, MDR was successfully implemented in the five pilot hospitals. During the six-month pilot-testing period, 105 data collection forms were completed – one for each registered maternal death in the five hospitals – and 69 (66%) were audited by the five local committees, leading to 69 corresponding audit report forms, including 78 recommendations. The number of participants

attending the audit meetings varied from three to eight (including managers but not systematically); one to four cases were reviewed during those meetings.

The cause of death was assessed by the audit committee in 84% of the cases. The main causes of death found by the audit committees were: haemorrhage, pre-eclampsia/eclampsia and uterine rupture. Some **48% of deaths were considered avoidable** according to national standards of care; **25% were considered as probably avoidable**. The most frequent recommendations were: (1) improving initial management of critical patients at the time of admission; (2) improving the availability of blood for transfusion; (3) improving patient monitoring during the postpartum period. The period of observation in survey 1 was not long enough to verify whether all recommendations were implemented or not.

These findings showed that MDR was **feasible** in various settings. Health professionals and service administrators were receptive and adhered relatively well to the process and the results of the audits, as evidenced by the number of maternal death cases audited, and the conclusions of the local audit committees (**adoption**).

Scaling up the solution in Mali and Senegal (survey 2)

A few years later, MDRs combined with educational activities were implemented on a larger scale in 23 referral hospitals in Senegal and Mali during the QUARITE trial [Dortonne 2009]. Characteristics of participating hospitals presented previously in Table 2 have shown that the healthcare facilities were representative of the existing health system in both countries, taking into account: the variety of contexts (urban versus rural), levels of care (primary- versus secondary-level referral health facilities) and the staff and resources availability.

According to the results of survey 2, the mean implementation score of the intervention reached 7.5 (minimum = 4 and maximum = 10) among the 23 participating hospitals, at the beginning of the intervention period (6 months after the initial training session). In each participating hospital, there was a multidisciplinary MDR committee whose members had been trained on maternal death reviews. Overall, these committees used the guidelines for MDR implementation but some of the data collection forms were not well understood, particularly the audit session report. Maternal death audit sessions had a slow start due to several factors: maternity personnel's workload, lack of confidence of local leaders, lack of cohesion within teams and lack of available personnel. The implementation score increased rapidly during

the following supervision visits. At the end of the first year of the implementation period, 22 out of the 23 intervention hospitals had a score of 10, showing that the **adoption of MDR was complete**.

Is the application acceptable to healthcare providers?

Participant observations and interviews with stakeholders were analysed to assess the acceptability of maternal death reviews during the pilot phase in Senegal (survey 1) and during the QUARITE trial in Mali and Senegal when MDR was combined with educational activities (survey 2).

Acceptability of audit alone (survey 1)

The qualitative analysis of the data sources of survey 1 in the five pilot-hospitals in Senegal led to the identification of various barriers to (Table 12) and facilitators of (Table 13) the implementation of maternal death reviews.

Barriers that were most frequently mentioned by interviewed personnel were: (1) poor quality of information in medical files; (2) lack of involvement of the head of department in the audit meetings; (3) lack of feedback to the staff who did not attend the audit meetings.

According to the health professionals interviewed, the perinatal information system in the pilot hospitals in Senegal was, in general, not suitable for allowing an extensive identification of all the maternal deaths occurring in hospitals. A midwife said:

“Many women die on their way to the hospital or during their admission to the facility: these deaths are not noted in the maternity department records.”

The lack of communication between different units in a given health facility was another barrier to the identification of maternal deaths occurring outside the maternity unit (for instance, in the general surgery unit or the intensive care unit). However, in certain health facilities, the designated data collector attended daily staff meetings to get information about maternal deaths that had occurred the day before and completed the registers when necessary. Some collectors even consulted admission registers or registers at the morgue to identify women who died on their way to the hospital or during admission. In two of the participating hospitals, registers or medical files were computerised, which greatly facilitated the data collector’s task of maternal deaths identification.

Table 12. Identified barriers to the implementation of maternal death reviews

Topics
<i>Factors influencing the identification of maternal death cases:</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Death occurring during the transportation of the woman to the hospital or shortly after admission • Death occurring outside of the maternity unit (i.e. in the intensive care unit)
<i>Factors influencing the data collection:</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor quality of information in medical files* • Data collection divided between numerous workers • Non-permanent collector in a health structure (medical student, resident) • Non-motivated collector • Inaccurate address in the medical files, preventing community inquiry
<i>Factors influencing the audit meetings:</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Head of department not involved in the audit meetings* • Poor quality of the collected information • Collector not invited to the audit meetings • Feeling of guilt from employees after audit meetings
<i>Factors influencing the use of the findings:</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of feedback to the staff who did not attend the audit meetings* • More deaths occurred in poor access settings
*Barriers most frequently mentioned by the interviewed personnel

The data collectors of all five hospitals deplored the poor quality of information in the medical files and stated that it was difficult to extract information concerning the itinerary of the woman before arriving in their health facility and the management of the patient after her admission in the maternity unit:

“Doctors sometimes did their diagnosis orally and noted nothing in the medical files, or patients arrived in such a serious state that there was no time to fill out the medical files....”

When verbal autopsy in the community was necessary and possible because the home was close to the hospital, the address provided in the medical files was inaccurate and residency of the deceased woman was not located. Professionals recognised that it was easier for a person with experience and a high

position in the hospital's hierarchy than a junior person to conduct interviews with other members of the staff, especially when enquiring about maternal death cases.

Even though audit meetings were regularly organised in all five pilot hospitals, the recommendations provided by our team concerning the audit process were not always followed. In particular, data collectors were not systematically invited to audit meetings; also, the number of participants was sometimes very low with few doctors (usually doctors).

In some of the hospitals, the weight of traditional command-chain relationships between doctors and other categories of personnel within the maternity unit was a barrier to establishing a multidisciplinary audit committee. This situation was one of the reasons why personnel were not eager to collect information on maternal deaths or to implement the audit committee's recommendations. Some of the professionals interviewed complained of a lack of communication between the audit committee and the staff:

"I was not invited to participate in the audit meetings and I was never informed of the conclusions. It was disappointing ..." (a surgical assistant)

One head of the maternity unit who was interviewed believed that only doctors could conduct an audit session: *"... because midwives and nurses were not qualified enough to give solutions and correct doctors ..."*

In certain cases, the midwives who participated in audit meetings considered the situation unnerving or even threatening:

"I felt guilty, even threatened by a punishment. The head of department said that the woman was killed when he talks about what happen in the unit when the patient died."

Conversely, in most of the hospitals where the head of the maternity unit did not attend the audit meetings, the employees were not eager to participate in the process, as they felt that their recommendations would not be implemented.

However, the research team identified various factors that facilitated MDR implementation in the pilot hospitals. **Facilitator** tools most frequently mentioned were: (1) a high level of professional qualifications

or experience of the data collector; (2) involvement of the head of the maternity unit, acting as a moderator during the audit meetings (Table 13).

Table 13. Identified facilitators to the implementation of maternal death reviews

Topics
<i>Factors influencing the identification of maternal death cases:</i>
• Daily identification of cases
• Consultation of many sources of data (hospital registers)
• Digitalisation of hospital registers
<i>Factors influencing the data collection:</i>
• High level of professional qualifications or experience of the data collector*
• Incentives for the data collector
• Quality of the collector’s training
• Interviews with the family members briefly before the exposure of the body
<i>Factors influencing the audit meetings:</i>
• Involvement of the head of department, acting as a moderator during the meeting*
• When possible, information from the community
• Short lapse of time between the death and the audit meeting
• Multidisciplinary meetings
<i>Factors influencing the use of the findings:</i>
• Feedback to the managers and all the staff of the maternity unit
• Involvement of the hospital officials
• Involvement of the community representatives

*Facilitators most frequently mentioned by the interviewed personnel

The professionals interviewed made several suggestions to improve the audit meetings, particularly the participation at these meetings:

- First, invite all employees to the meetings, or at least one representative of each category of professionals.
- Providing a free catering service during the meetings would also motivate people to attend and would create a more pleasant atmosphere during these sessions.

- Furthermore, the organisation of the meeting shortly after the death occurred and introducing the information obtained from the community when a visit to the family or relatives had been possible, would allow a deeper analysis and stimulate more discussion about the case.
- According to the interviews, the head of department must always attend these meetings and play a moderating role.
- Conclusions of the audit meetings should be communicated to hospital administration and regional authorities.
- Feedback to health workers should be formalised as a memo posted in the staff room; the information in the memo should be anonymous.

The acceptability of audit combined with education (survey 2)

I took into account the suggestions of health stakeholders to design the multi-faceted intervention that was later assessed in the QUARITE trial. If the audit were to result in a change, there must be willingness to identify problems, with leadership capable and willing to implement changes. The involvement and leadership of those in charge of maternity services (doctor and midwife) play a vital role in implementing audits and preventing negative effects from the intervention. The findings of the survey 1 helped me to understand that the capacity of health services managers to ensure such leadership depends on key aptitudes: (i) knowledge of the evidence-based practice of the main obstetric complications; (ii) understanding of non-medical reasons of maternal death (social, economic, cultural, and legal dimensions of maternal mortality); and (iii) a mastery of the clinical audit approach. Thereby, I decided to combine the audit with educational activities using the Society of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists of Canada ALARM (Advances in Labour And Risk Management) International Program. The fourth edition of this program used adult learning techniques to teach essential evidence-based obstetric skills, maternal death audit techniques and sexual and reproductive rights [ALARM 2007].

The results of survey 2 showed that the maternal death audit was very **well accepted when supported with education**. Hospitals planned regular meetings for MDR during the second year of the intervention period and all intervention hospitals provided regular on-site training on emergency obstetric care. Quarterly visits by a trained external facilitator and on-site training facilitated MDR in providing healthcare professionals with the necessary knowledge to make relevant recommendations to improve the quality of care.

During the 2-year intervention period, the 23 hospitals audited 673 maternal deaths. Out of these deaths, **223 (33%) were considered certainly avoidable** according to the conclusions of the audit committees, **270 (40%) probably avoidable** and **117 (17%) non-avoidable**. 320 maternal deaths (65%) were considered certainly or probably avoidable because of inappropriate treatment after obstetric complications, 123 (25%) because of diagnosis errors, 89 (18%) because of inappropriate monitoring during post-partum and 84 (17%) because of insufficient evaluation of the woman at hospital admission.

Actions recommended by the audit committees to prevent maternal deaths varied considerably between centres and were context-specific, in order to ensure the **acceptability of the recommendations** (Table 14).

Table 14. Example of recommendations in the QUARITE trial (2008-2009)

Resources and management	Recommendations mainly implemented	Recommendations rarely implemented
Staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-site training focusing on the identification of problems of patients care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regular assessment of medical charts by senior staff (Ob-Gyn or Midwife)
Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Posters of clinical guidelines are placed on the wall of the maternity unit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Equipment orders for the laboratory or the radiology Essential material orders (blood pressure device, dipstick proteinuria, vacuum, etc.)
Drugs and supplies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Orders of essential drugs lacking in the hospital (i.e. Magnesium sulfate, antibiotics, misoprostol, etc. ...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Essential drugs package available 24/24 in the maternity unit List of donors or blood collection in the community
Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of a specific form to monitor patients with severe / life-threatening complications Other colleagues called systematically when a complication arises (post-partum haemorrhage, eclampsia, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication and feedback to healthcare facility which refer critical ill patients Information / communication in the community (i.e. women group)

Although the nature and focus of recommendations drawn up during MDR, varied from one hospital to another, concrete interventions were **implemented comprehensively** to improve the quality of care in all intervention hospitals. **Organisational changes to improve 24 h service availability and patient**

monitoring contributed the most to improving emergency obstetric care and, as a consequence, to improving maternal outcomes. The mainly implemented recommendations contributed to affordability as there were no costs resulting from the new processes and they were quite simple in use.

Is the application economically viable for the settings in which it is intended?

The healthcare system perspective is adopted for the cost analysis in survey 3. All costs are adjusted according to inflation (5%) and discounting (3%). Costs are separated into two categories: launching costs at the start of the intervention and recurrent costs during the intervention period. Launching costs included: financial resources and time for the preparatory work (set-up of the program at national level and direct costs of the initial training of the opinion leaders (acquisition of teaching materials, hiring of the conference room, per diems, cost of time spent). Recurrent costs are: the personal costs of staff spending time on the audits cycle and on-site training activities; annual meeting costs (per diems, personal costs, conference room facilities) and costs regarding supervision visits (vehicles, per diem and salaries). A four-year overview was used for the cost calculation (2007 basis in €): year 1 of the QUARITE trial consisted of the preparation of the program; the training and MDR activities occurred in year 2 and 3; and year 4 was the period of audit practice without supervision by an external facilitator.

The cost in each country included three sub-costs: (1) program costs for setting up the initial training, (2) costs for supervision and coordination activities, and (3) costs for audits and on-site training activities. Part (1) remained the same for each country. Part (2) and (3) varied according to the level of engagement of healthcare professionals in audit activities. A unit cost was calculated for each activity. For example, the unit cost for one supervision visit was calculated and multiplied by the number of visits per year. To better reflect local contexts, different unit costs for audit cycle activities were calculated according to each category of hospital (hospital in the capital city, regional hospital and district hospital).

Table 15: Cost assessments of the intervention program

Cost Category	Senegal	Mali
Program costs (training, material, etc.)	€80 519	€80 519
Coordination (supervision, annual meetings, etc.)	€193 340	€229 029
Audit cycle and on-site training activities	€198 343	€149 866
Total	€472 202	€459 414

Table 15 presents the results on the total costs after the four years of implementation of the QUARITE trial. Program costs represented around 17% of the total cost in both countries. Costs for coordination and supervision represented 41% of the total costs in Senegal and 50% in Mali. This cost is influenced by the salaries and per diems allowed for people involved in the activities of supervision and, to a lesser extent, by the fuel used for supervision tours. Audit cycle activities represent 42% of the total cost in Senegal and 33% in Mali. These costs are lower in Mali than in Senegal. The difference is due to the lowest personal costs, where the salary rates for midwives and doctors may be 3 times lower than in Senegal. Variation in costs between hospital categories for participating in audits and learning sessions exist. For example, in Senegal more people attended the on-site learning sessions in national-level hospitals, but fewer people attended the audit sessions, compared to district hospitals. In Mali, we observed the opposite. Overall, there was no pattern showing that total costs of audit activities were higher for a particular type of hospital.

Our results show that the total cost of multifaceted intervention is **affordable**, and the total amount of resources required for four years **represented less than 1%** of the resources allocated for referral hospitals in these countries during the same period (de Roodenbeke, E 2010). However, external support could be needed, especially for the launching costs. Countries could modify some components of the program (such as less training or less supervision) to alleviate costs, but the experience of the QUARITE trial in Mali and Senegal has shown the equal importance of training with appropriate teaching materials and of strong support from the national level by regular on-site visits. Moreover, allowing the staff-at a local and at a regional level to share their experiences about the program and present the achievements once a year could be really important for the **uptake** of the intervention.

The opportunity costs of conducting MDR in facilities are not high, compared to other program costs. One of the counter-arguments would be that the staff “wasted time” implementing the audit cycle. This argument is poor as salaries are low. But results in our survey 3 with QUARITE participants show that hospitals did a mean of n=6 and n=7 audits and learning sessions respectively per year, with a duration time of around 3 h for each activity. Other activities such as completing reports and data collection do not represent a considerable amount of time. Compared to the potential benefits of the audits, the total amount of time spent on audit cycles (approximately 18 h per year plus training attendance) is a minimum cost that facilities should bear in order to see some changes in care practices and maternity organisation.

I have only found one paper that examines the costs of implementing a national audit program for perinatal mortality [Pattinson 2009]. The running cost at the national level was of \$US 35 000 per year and included software program maintenance and development costs, office costs, collecting data, report printing, attendance at workshops and technical task team meetings. Personal costs for attending audit sessions by staff was undocumented. This clearly shows that this cost assessment study in the QUARITE trial brings a new perspective in a low-resource setting with the argument that the audit is affordable.

However, important study limitations should be mentioned:

- The first limit is related to the challenge on the evaluation of costs of a complex intervention, such as MDR. I tried to take into account the multiple ingredients of the intervention itself and the heterogeneity of the context (different types of hospitals). Results are therefore a first estimation and other country-specific considerations (e.g. geography and roads, staff turnover, etc.) may arise if the intervention is indeed implemented.
- The second limitation is related to the hypothesis that the solution would not require additional human resources in hospital, but policy makers should consider that in specific context, there might be a need for additional trained staff (e.g. a gynaecologist) to ensure a sufficient level of competence and deliver the program successfully.
- The third limitation is linked to the management of health programs at national and regional levels. Estimations provided in this paper do not take into account possible “joint costs” with other national programs in place (e.g. vaccination day programs). For example, we could have designed an intervention where supervision visits are combined with vaccination’s program representative tours (or other programs) in order to alleviate the program costs related to supervision.

Regarding the **scaling up opportunity of the program to other countries**, this could definitely be an ambition of the program if two conditions are thoroughly considered in advance by policy makers to use this program as a strategy for reducing maternal and neonatal mortality:

- Firstly, the QUARITE trial hospitals received a high level of support from the national coordinator, who was a strong facilitator in conducting the audits. Thereby, the Ministry of Health's commitment to the program is necessary to ensure the supervision rounds considered as essential for the audit implementation. Without commitment and financial support at the national level for coordination costs, it is unlikely that audits will be implemented in the long term in the participating hospitals.
- Time spent by healthcare professionals for audit activities is critical to the success of the program at hospital level. Local managers' commitment to the program is necessary to dedicate working time of health practitioners to audit activities.

If these two conditions are met, the solution has the potential for **rapid scaling up** to other hospitals in low-income countries, thanks to the ease of use by local stakeholders and affordability at a hospital level.

Is the solution usable by facility-based health workers?

Interviews with health services managers and healthcare practitioners carried out in survey 3 were analysed to assess the degree to which each step of the audit circle (Figure 1) was implemented as it was designed in the protocol (**fidelity**), and to verify whether maternal death auditing was usable by different categories of health workers to improve quality of care.

Identification of maternal death and data collection

An essential step to conduct MDR in a proper manner is the data collection on maternal deaths. We observed that insufficient record keeping could impact the analysis of cases and the relevance of recommendations. I showed that the data collection in the maternity wards could be improved as part of quality assurance programs [Dumont 2012]. Information routinely collected by health professionals (medical files, partograms and registers) should be used to develop a valid information system that would help the data collector to collect reliable information on each maternal death.

Moreover the choice of the person to assume the role of data collector seemed to have greatly influenced the implementation of the MDR in the health facilities. We realised that data collection was generally less efficient when it was divided among several people, or when the task was assigned to a student, a resident or a permanent employee who had little motivation for this work. Interviewed data collectors confirmed that performing interviews with the staff and the family of the deceased woman was emotionally difficult. An experienced or senior staff in the hospital's command chain, who is well respected in the community, may collect the information more easily than a younger employee or a subordinate. However, the person conducting this kind of interview should be very tactful and sensitive. He or she should be aware of the concept of the different delays that limit women's access to healthcare services. Generally, the data collection procedure encountered no major problems when the task was assigned to a professional who had experience and to whom this kind of work was part of his or her field of competence. An example of such an individual would be a midwife who was also responsible for the coordination of services in the maternity unit or at the district or regional level.

Analysis of the findings

For audit meetings, the process is slightly different as there must be a willingness to identify problems, leadership skills and willingness to institute changes to achieve positive results. According to our MDR experience in various contexts, most of the deaths that occurred in referral hospitals were preventable. Effective and cheap interventions exist to prevent death from the major causes, including haemorrhage, hypertensive disease, sepsis and septic abortion. The issue would be to implement these solutions in view of local contexts, resource constraints and cultural norms. The initial training of **health services managers** (doctors and midwives) and the sequence of several educational activities during the 2-year implementation period of the QUARITE trial aimed at developing local leadership and empowering health workers. Regular visits by a trained external facilitator plus on-site training facilitated maternal death reviews by providing healthcare professionals the necessary knowledge and confidence to make quality improvement suggestions during the audit sessions.

Recommendations and actions

Another key issue of the audit process is the recommendations for action that should be relevant to the context, the scientific knowledge and available resources and the potential of implementation in a short-time period. According to survey 3 during the post-intervention period of the QUARITE trial, I analysed all the recommendations that were written in the audit reports and verified whether all these recommendations were effectively implemented or not. The objective of this analysis was to assess if health workers of the facility had the necessary knowledge and training to use MDR to prevent maternal and neonatal deaths.

Table 20 presents the most frequent recommendations that were written in the audit reports. Among 1059 recommendations drawn by the different audit committees in the 23 intervention hospitals of the QUARITE trial, more than half of the recommendations were related to the availability of medical services, the development or update of care protocols, continuing education, transfusion and availability of drugs. These results are consistent with the barriers to quality care identified during the audit sessions in the participating hospitals or reported in existing literature.

The results also showed limited implementation of the specific recommendations, particularly those requiring managerial support. This finding could be explained by general poor attendance of **hospital managers** to the audit sessions and lack of feedback of the suggested recommendations to the managers to act accordingly. The “WHO Beyond the numbers” manual recommends hospitals and service managers take part in the MDRs in order for them to understand the issues properly and to work on recommendations with other professionals [Beyond the numbers 2004]. The participation of managers in the audit session is then essential to build teamwork, to facilitate the review of maternal death in a constructive way and to plan appropriate and realistic actions to prevent other maternal deaths. Inadequate feedback to members of the audit team about the implementation of recommendations was also reported by some personnel interviewed, as most of the participants did not know whether the suggested recommendations were conclusive or not; nor who was responsible for implementation.

Implementation of the recommendations may also be strongly influenced by **the leadership of the head of the maternity unit**. In the hospitals where local leadership was inadequate, healthcare professionals described the situation as unnerving or even threatening and the feedback of audit results and

recommendations was ineffective. In the hospitals where the head of the maternity unit was involved in the audit process, the audit approach was generally accepted by health professionals and recommendations highly implemented.

Table 20: Recommendations written in the audit reports and implemented during the QUARITE trial by category (23 hospitals in Senegal and Mali)

Category of recommendation	Written	Implemented	Ratio
Improve the 24h availability of services	167	33	20%
Development/updating clinical guidelines	134	78	58%
Training of healthcare professionals	132	48	36%
Improve availability and use of transfusion	123	17	14%
Improve availability of drugs	89	26	29%
Improve record keeping	77	41	53%
Improve the referral system	74	26	35%
Enhance patient monitoring in post-partum	71	42	59%
Improve interpersonal communication	63	27	43%
Define tasks for each category of personnel	52	17	33%
Inform and educate the community	35	5	14%
Improve the quality of prenatal care	22	4	18%
Improve financial access to health services	20	4	20%
Total	1059	368	35%

Participatory observations during audit sessions show that the hierarchy within participating hospitals had a great impact on social relationships among healthcare professionals. The findings stressed the important

role of the head of the maternity unit in reducing hierarchical boundaries, promoting a multidisciplinary approach and increasing staff adherence to the audit recommendations.

The level of implementation of the written recommendations also varied according to the category of the targeted population by the actions recommended (Table 21). The results show limited implementation of recommendations that target prenatal and postpartum care. Most of the clinical recommendations likely to emerge were very similar to the evidence-based guidelines for the Advances in Labour and Risk Management International Program [ALARM 2007] that were taught to local opinion leaders at the beginning of the intervention period. Less frequently discussed topics during the training sessions were prenatal and postpartum care topics. This may be the reason why workable solutions for poor quality care during pregnancy or post-partum were poorly implemented.

Table 21: Recommendations written in the audit reports and actually implemented during the QUARITE trial according to targeted population (23 hospitals in Senegal and Mali)

Targeted population	Written recommendation (a)	Recommendations implemented (b)	Ratio b/a
Women in labour or delivery	653	225	34%
Women with post-partum haemorrhage	186	53	28%
Women with pre-eclampsia	75	43	57%
Pregnant women (prenatal care)	59	8	14%
Women with sepsis	23	8	35%
Whole population	22	3	14%
Women with other direct complication	16	15	94%
Women with other indirect complication	16	8	50%
Women in post-partum	9	4	44%
Women with prolonged obstructed labour	1	1	100%
Total	1059	368	35%

GENERAL CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this research provides evidence that, when supported with education, maternal death reviews can prevent some maternal and neonatal deaths in low-income countries and were **reproducible** in different categories of referral hospitals of intended use in Senegal and Mali. Health professionals and service administrators were generally **receptive** and **adhered** relatively well to the process and the results of the audits, as evidenced by the number of maternal death cases audited, and the relevance of the recommendations drawn by the local audit committees. On-site training in selected topics facilitates MDR by providing healthcare professionals with the accurate knowledge and confidence to make quality improvement suggestions. According to the costs associated with building the intervention at a national level and the implementation costs at a hospital level, the application is **economically viable** for the settings in which it is intended. The MDR approach is **well accepted** by health professionals and **easy to use** when the information collected for the audit is appropriate and local leadership is strong enough to promote non-threatening and multidisciplinary audit meetings. **Since we selected different hospitals with various characteristics in Senegal and Mali, these results could be expanded to other health facilities in other countries with similar contexts to West Africa.**

Experience of MDR or audit programs has increased in the past years in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) with **positive results** in terms of modification of staff practices and increase of the overall quality of care [Pattinson 2009]. National scaling-up of these interventions is under consideration around the world, but some countries face difficulties with conducting maternal death reviews [Kongnyuy 2008]. To prevent the wide variability in uptake and quality of the MDR process, the World Health Organization (WHO) and partners introduced a new approach in 2012 to ensure more robust collection and use of information for action [WHO 2012]. **This new approach**, named **“Maternal Death Surveillance and Response” (MDSR)**, represents a continuous cycle of identification, notification and review of maternal deaths followed by interpretation of review findings, response and action. Whilst the maternal death review (MDR) component of MDSR is now well established, **“surveillance” in MDSR emphasises the need for more accurate and complete data on numbers of maternal deaths, and the “response” involves formulating and implementing targeted recommendations.** The continuous cycle provides the means for countries to aggregate and link information on the causes of and factors associated with maternal death

and to examine this data to develop and implement a coordinated local and national response to prevent future deaths.

WHO, with UNFPA, recently initiated the Global MDSR Implementation Survey [WHO 2016] among member states, which aims to provide information on the degree of implementation and allow tracking of progress over time. The first survey was completed in 2015 and included country progress data and case studies describing the MDSR implementation. The findings for African countries (Kenya, Nigeria, Cameroon and Malawi) are in accordance with the results of our implementation research in Mali and Senegal. **MDR was often introduced by governments within a context of global commitment to the elimination of maternal deaths**, broad national political support and an increasing number of laws, policies and programs directed at improving maternal health.

Healthcare professionals are less likely to report maternal deaths and provide information about maternal deaths if they fear punitive action. Therefore, a confidential and non-punitive system, as implemented in the Republic of South Africa, is another key factor for success. While the Ministries of Health were the key drivers in implementing policies to facilitate MDR at a national level, UN agencies (WHO, UNFPA, UNICEF) and professional organisations of gynaecologists and obstetricians also played key roles. According to case-study findings, common barriers were identified in countries where MDR systems were less well developed: inexperience in MDR processes, resistance to changing practices, low level of human or material resources, or pre-existing problems of work organisation. Provider characteristics perceived need for innovation in hospitals and leadership of the program champion are also likely to influence the MDR activities held in participating hospitals. For program activities, coordination and supervision could be affected negatively by car or road problems and financial and time constraints.

Finally, the results of our implementation research in Senegal and Mali could help policy makers and contribute to the success of the MDSR in other countries. Essential knowledge and training is necessary to use the solution in a satisfactory manner:

1. Prior enhancement of the perinatal information system is necessary in many contexts. Hospital administration must help the health workers archive different data sources to be able to gain access to them easily, or even record selected information in a computerised system. Medical files must be classified and organised in a specific room, which should be locked at all times to preserve

confidentiality. With regard to record keeping, training in partogram filling should be proposed if needed.

2. Appropriate choice and training of the data collector is essential. The data collector should be an experienced professional who has a senior position in the hospital command chain. The objectives of initial training are: to improve competence in interviewing staff and family members after a maternal death; to carry out the door-to-door approach to describe the patient's management within the health system and to synthesise the information for the audit committee.
3. Appropriate training of the head of the maternity unit is usually needed to increase his or her leadership. The objectives of such training are to improve his or her knowledge of best practices and of the social, economic, cultural and legal factors that hinder women's access to essential services, as well as audit procedures and teaching techniques to adults.
4. Appropriate training of the entire team in the audit process is necessary to facilitate its implementation. This training should be offered within the hospitals to avoid lack of personnel during working days. It should target health professionals who provide obstetrical care, reviewing the top maternal killers and suggesting essential tools and problem management with the goal of improving care for mothers and newborns. To meet the needs for best practices training, the topics must be selected by the audit committee depending on the principal causes of maternal mortality in a given hospital, as identified during the reviews.

REFERENCES

ALARM. Advances in Labour And Risk Management 4th edition. 2007 [<http://iwhp.sogc.org/>]. Ottawa: Society of obstetricians and gynaecologists of Canada

Aqil A, Lippeveld T, Hozumi D. PRISM framework: a paradigm shift for designing, strengthening and evaluating routine health information systems. *Health Policy Plan* 2009;24:217–28.

Beyond the Numbers: Reviewing maternal deaths and complications to make pregnancy safer. World Health Organization, Geneva; 2004.

Briand V, Dumont A, Abrahamowicz M, Traore M, Rozenberg P, Watier L, Fournier P. Maternal and perinatal outcomes by mode of delivery in Senegal and Mali: a cross-sectional epidemiological survey. *PLoS ONE* 2012; 7(10): e47352. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0047352.

Chaillet N, Dubé E, Dugas M, Audibert F, Tourigny C, Fraser WD, Dumont A. Evidence-based Strategies for Implementing Guidelines in Obstetrics: A Systematic Review. *Obstet Gynecol*, 2006 Nov;108(5):1234.

de Roodenbeke E. La politique hospitalière et le financement de l'hôpital en Afrique. World Bank Institute, 2010: <http://info.worldbank.org/etools/docs/library>.

Devane D, Begley CM, Clarke M, Horey D. Evaluating maternity care: a core set of outcome measures. *Birth* 2007;34:164-72.

Dortonne JR, Dumont A, Traore M, Perreault G, Couturier F, Kanouté K..Maternal mortality audits in low-resource countries: analysis of 23 hospitals in Senegal and Mali (the QUARITE study). *J Obstet Gynaecol Can* 2009 ; 31 :936–944.

Dumont A. (dir.), Traoré M. (dir.), Dortonne J.R. (dir.) *Audit des décès maternels dans les établissements de santé : guide de mise en oeuvre*. Marseille : IRD, 2014, 167 p. (Didactiques). ISBN 978-2-7099-1855-8.

Dumont A, Fournier P, Abrahamowicz M, Traoré M, Haddad S, Fraser W. QUARITE (quality of care, risk management, and technology in obstetrics): a cluster-randomized trial of a multifaceted intervention to reduce hospital-based maternal mortality in Senegal and Mali. *Lancet* 2013; 382:146-157.

Dumont A, Fournier P, Fraser W, et al. QUARITE (quality of care, risk management and technology in obstetrics): a cluster-randomized trial of a multifaceted intervention to improve emergency obstetric care in Senegal and Mali. *Trials* 2009; 10: 85.

Dumont A, Gaye A, de Bernis L, et al. Facility-based maternal death reviews: effects on maternal mortality in a district hospital in Senegal. *Bull World Health Organ* 2006; 84: 218–24.

Dumont A, Gueye M, Sow A, Diop I, Konate KM, Dambé P, Abrahamowicz A, Fournier P. Utilisation des données recueillies en routine pour évaluer l'activité des maternités au Mali et au Sénégal (essai QUARITE). *Rev Epidemiol Santé Publique* 2012; 60 : 489-496.

Dumont A, Tourigny C, Fournier P. Improving obstetric care in low-resource settings: implementation of facility-based maternal death reviews in five pilot hospitals in Senegal. *Hum Resour Health* 2009; 7: 61.

Fournier P, Dumont A, Tourigny C, Dunkley G, Dramé S. Improved access to comprehensive emergency obstetric care and its effect on institutional maternal mortality in rural Mali. *Bull World Health Organ* 2009; 87: 30–38.

Hogan MC, Foreman KJ, Naghavi M, et al. Maternal mortality for 181 countries, 1980-2008: a systematic analysis of progress towards Millennium Development Goal 5. *Lancet* 2010; 375: 1609–23.

Jamtvedt G, Young JM, Kristoffersen DT, et al. Audit and feedback: effects on professional practice and health care outcomes. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2006(2): CD000259.

Kongnyuy EJ, Leigh B, van den Broek N. Effect of audit and feedback on the availability, utilisation and quality of emergency obstetric care in three districts in Malawi. *Women Birth* 2008; 21: 149–55.

Kongnyuy EJ, van den Broek N. The difficulties of conducting maternal death reviews in Malawi. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* 2008; 8:42.

Maine D, Ward V, Kamara A. The design and evaluation of maternal mortality programs. Center for Population and Family Health. New York: Columbia University; 1997. p. 1-126.

Mak G, Djénépo F, Kone G, Haddad S. Combien ça coûte? In : Dumont A (Dir.), Traoré M (Dir.), Dortonne JR. (Dir.) *Audit des décès maternels dans les établissements de santé : guide de mise en oeuvre*. Marseille : IRD, 2014, P. 37-42. (DIDACTIQUES). ISBN 978-2-7099-1855-8

Martey JO, Djan JO, Twum S, Browne EN, Opoku SA. Maternal mortality due to hemorrhage in Ghana. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet* 1993; 42: 237–41.

Mbaruku G, Bergstrom S. Reducing maternal mortality in Kigoma, Tanzania. *Health Policy Plan* 1995; 10: 71–8.

Otchere SA; Kayo A. The challenges of improving emergency obstetric care in two rural districts in Mali. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet* 2007; 99: 173-82.

Pattinson, R., Kerber, K., Waiswa, P., Day, L. T., Mussell, F., Asiruddin, S. K., et al. (2009). Perinatal mortality audit: counting, accountability, and overcoming challenges in scaling up in low- and middle-income countries. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet*, 107 Suppl 1, S113-121, S121-112.

Pattinson, R., Kerber, K., Waiswa, P., Day, L. T., Mussell, F., Asiruddin, S. K., et al. (2009). Perinatal mortality audit: counting, accountability, and overcoming challenges in scaling up in low- and middle-income countries. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet*, 107 Suppl 1, S113-121, S121-112

Shah A, Faundes A, Machoki Mi, Et Al. Methodological considerations in implementing the who global survey for monitoring maternal and perinatal health. *Bull world health organ* 2008; 86: 126–31.

Van Den Akker T, Van Rhenen J, Mwangomba B, Lommerse K, Vinkhumbo S, Van Roosmalen J. Reduction of severe acute maternal morbidity and maternal mortality in thyolo district, malawi: the impact of obstetric audit. *Plos one* 2011; 6: e20776.

Witter S, Dieng T, Mbengue D, Moreira I, De Brouwere V. The national free delivery and caesarean policy in Senegal: evaluating process and outcomes. *Health Policy Plan* 2010; 25(5): 384–92.

World Health Organization. Global Monitoring of Implementation of Maternal Death Surveillance and Response (MDSR) Geneva: World Health Organization, 2016. http://www.who.int/maternal_child_adolescent/epidemiology/maternal-deaths-surveillance/global-monitoring/en/ Accessed: 26 June 2017

World Health Organization. Maternal Death Surveillance and Response: technical guidance information for action to prevent maternal deaths. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2013. http://www.who.int/maternal_child_adolescent/documents/maternal_death_surveillance/en/ Accessed: 26 June 2017